

WWF/SANBI
GRASSLAND BIOME PROJECT

LUNEBURG
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT
AND GRAZING MANAGEMENT

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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT AND GRAZING MANAGEMENT

Lüneburg WWF SA / SANBI - Agriculture and Conservation Demonstration Project

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1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Lüneburg Veld Condition Assessments

The Lüneburg Farming Area is identified together with the Wakkerstroom Townlands by WWF-SA as important areas where guidelines on the specific grazing and fire management are required.

Baseline grassland surveys are therefore necessary to determine the current veld condition and to make recommendations on veld management that will assist in the conservation of these important grassland areas. According to Mucina and Rutherford's vegetation map, both the Lüneburg and Wakkerstroom grasslands fall within the Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland (Veld Type Gm 14).

Maps of the farms in this study area are appended.

1.2 Veld condition assessment and interpretation of past land-use practices

The traditional burning/grazing management practice in the Lüneburg area is to burn in autumn, followed by grazing by sheep in the winter. These areas are then grazed by sheep, specifically for the purpose of providing nutritious green grazing for the lambs. After the autumn burns are burned and grazed in the winter, a rest from grazing is allowed for 18 months before the next autumn burn.

However with some farms the grazing period on these burned grasslands are longer than 6 months and the farms are then managed as a two-camp system. These areas are also burned in autumn, followed by continuous grazing by sheep for 11 months.

With some farms Cattle are utilizing 'old grass' areas (areas ungrazed by sheep) and graze the Lüneburg grasslands mostly in summer after spring burns.

While veld condition assessments are expected to be a reflection the current stocking rates, past grazing history is not always known or even with the knowledge of the past grazing history there may be a trend of improvement or deterioration in veld condition. This trend will become clear after regular (at least three) veld condition assessments.

With this study the veld condition will be assessed and management recommendations will be given for the purpose of improving the production potential of the grazing and to improve veld condition. It is believed that this can be done whilst flora diversity is maintained at the same time.

Generally the species composition of the grassland will reflect the past management actions or land-use practices.

Too much burning followed by over-grazing will have an impact on certain grass species. Under-utilization, where an area is over protected against fire when fire should be a natural part of the management system, will have a specific impact on the grass layer. A lack of grazing, or a wrong balance in the feeding or grazing spectrum will also have a specific impact on the grass layer.

Grass species can be classified according to their reaction to burning and grazing. See paragraph 2.5 for the definitions of the terms "*Decreasers*" and "*Increasers*". Some grassland areas are subject to heavy grazing pressure from cattle, where the terms "selectively grazed" or "over-rested" apply. Areas dominated - for instance - by species, such as *Loudetia simplex* (Common Russet Grass) as a result of selective grazing are grouped within the Increaser 1 category.

The category containing Increaser 1 species therefore describe grasses that are either *moisture loving* or species typical of *selective grazing*, or both (*Pers. Comm. Prof W.S.W. Trollope*). The Increaser 1 category species are also grass species that increase in its abundance where grasslands, in the absence of grazing, are protected against fire for long periods or where the grasslands, in the absence of grazing, have been *burned infrequently*.

These Increaser 1 species are typically found between rocky areas or areas where the soil moisture is high, such as at wetlands (or stream bank ecotones).

A higher Increaser 1 component is therefore expected at wetland areas.

Other species opportunistically establish itself after disturbance and should have been grouped with the Increaser 2 category, species that increase in abundance when grasslands are disturbed or degraded by too frequent burning or through overgrazing. However, Thatch Grass species are often quick to establish and dominate, even at areas where some form of mechanical disturbance has taken place. Thatch Grass species are grouped with Increaser 1 species instead.

The corrective action of resting the grassland will not be effective with Thatch Grass or even with grass species that increase with selective grazing. Resting such areas will exacerbate the problem even further. That is why Thatch Grass is not grouped with Increaser 2 species but with the Increaser 1 species.

Likewise Common Russet Grass is not grouped as an Increaser 3 species (species that increase with selective grazing) but grouped with Increaser 1 species. Increased burning and controlled grazing would allow other species to establish itself under conditions of reduced dominance (height dominance) of Thatch Grass, which is palatable in its early growth stages.

The persistence and dominance of Thatch Grass, once it has established itself, is problematic and a challenge to manage – for the dominance of a tall grass species is generally contrary to grassland management objectives (dominance in height affects maximum species diversity and basal cover and the mature grass is not palatable due to the woodiness of the grass culms).

A veld condition assessment should therefore reveal whether the grassland area has been well managed (i.e. burnt frequently enough) or mismanaged (i.e. over-rested, overgrazed, degraded, disturbed, or too frequently burnt).

1.3 Veld condition monitoring and grass species dynamics

The veld condition assessment on these grasslands will serve as a baseline for long term monitoring. Veld condition information sampled from the grassland sites should be updated, by the means of surveys, on a regular (i.e. yearly) basis in order to detect trends and direction of compositional change. In so doing, timely changes can be made in the management practices (i.e. stocking rates, burning, etc.), if necessary.

1.4 Management Models

Quantitative information which is representative of the veld type found will be useful for the construction of management models specific to the environmental conditions of these grasslands.

Veld management models for each of the ecological units represented on these grasslands should be set up as part of a long term monitoring strategy. These models will reflect the impact which management has on the species composition, whether by burning (fire) or grazing, i.e. within for the specific veld type conditions.

1.5 Management Objectives

Management objectives should be clearly defined. Generally grassland monitoring will determine whether the objective is reached or not. The management models will also show how the grass composition is changing relative to the benchmark for the specific ecological units. It will also measure the success of the recommended management strategy.

2. METHODS

2.1 Grass species composition

A line transect is undertaken within a homogenous grassland area. In this study a total of 100 sampling points are taken within each site. The sampling points are 1 m apart. At each sampling point the nearest grass species is recorded.

The number of times each grass species are encountered in each site is recorded as the percentage (%) frequency¹.

2.2 Bare ground

Bare ground is expressed as frequency (%) out of the total number of samplings in the site. It is recorded if no perennial grass species is found within 30 cm from the sampling point.

Bare ground may be encountered with shallow soils where rocky outcrops are common or may be found in rare cases where the grassland has been severely degraded.

2.3 Forbs, Sedges, Annual Grasses, Weeds (exotic invaders) and Biodiversity or Total Herbaceous Dicotyledonous Plant Diversity

2.3.1 Forbs, Sedges, Annual Grasses, Weeds

If any of the above-mentioned plants is found closer than the perennial grass species it is recorded separately.

The presence of forbs or annual grasses or weeds may indicate disturbance or degradation. The presence of sedges indicates the wetness of the soil at the site.

2.3.2 Flora diversity

Herbaceous dicotyledonous forbs are included in biodiversity (or flora diversity) surveys separately from grassland condition surveys, where the condition of the grass layer is based on the composition and frequency abundance of grass species in different ecological categories. Biodiversity surveys are plot surveys and not line transects, but the surface area of the same grassland monitoring site is often utilized to survey non-grass (or forb-) plant diversity. A total of 15 sub-plots are assessed in a random fashion within the grassland monitoring site in an area of 2500 m². Plant diversity is assessed by recording the abundance per species within different classes (i.e. 1-3 individual plants of a species = class 2, 4-6 individuals of a species = class 5 and 7-9 individuals of a species = class 8). Plant diversity is analysed using the Statistical S and/or Shannon-Wiener Diversity Index Method (Colwell, 2005).

2. 4 Plant Cover and Organic Material Accumulation

In addition to the monitoring of grass species composition, observations are made of the vegetation cover indexes (average tuft distances, strikes and phytomass). Organic material accumulation is recorded in a scale of 1 to 5, where 5 = very high and 1 very low. (Woody cover in savanna areas is also recorded by observing and documenting any branches extending over the sampling points).

2. 4. 1 Average tuft distances

The grass basal cover is recorded by measuring the distance of the nearest individual tuft from every random sampling point. The further the tufts are apart, the larger the distance measured between them and the monitoring rod.

¹ Grass species frequencies are used within the Key Grass Species method.

2. 4. 2 Strikes or hits

The number of times that the monitoring rod hit the rooted or basal parts of the grass tuft is also recorded. The more strikes the higher the cover.

2. 4. 3 Fuel load or Phytomass

The compressed grass height, measured by a disc meter, is used to calculate the grass volume or standing phytomass.

The disc is dropped vertically, 100 times within the site. The average height of the compressed grass is used to calculate the fuel load or phytomass. The calibration curve of Trollope and Potgieter (1986) is used to calculate the phytomass.

The compressed height of the disc on the grass layer is related to the grass weight. The phytomass is expressed as kilograms of dry grass per unit area (ha). This will be useful when assessing the fuel load of the grass layer.

2.5 The Key Grass Species Technique

The assessment of range or veld condition provides the means of tracking trends in the condition of the veld involving either an improvement or degradation, and to formulate veld management practices for livestock farming or wild life systems.

This can be a daunting and difficult task for the farmer/game manager as a wide knowledge of grass species and their identification is required. The Key Grass Species technique was developed by Professor Winston Trollope to assist veld managers with the assessment of veld condition.

It was designed to be simple, practical and effective and encompasses the basic knowledge of grasses that most farmers already possess. Instead of having to identify all the grass species in order to follow trends brought about by management practices, the land user now only has to identify the few key grass species that are indicators of good or poor management practices.

Veld condition refers to the condition of the vegetation in relation to some functional characteristic/s (Trollope, et.al., 1990) and in the case of livestock production based on grassland vegetation comprises the potential of the grass sward to produce forage for grazers, grass fuel to support controlled burns and its resistance to accelerated soil erosion as influenced by the basal and aerial cover of the grass sward.

The following procedure was used for developing the key grass species technique for assessing veld condition:

- Identify and list all the grass species occurring in the study area noting their identification characteristics for use in the field.
- Based on careful observations in the field and consultations with local land users, subjectively classify all the known grass species in the area into Decreaser and Increaser species according to their reaction to a grazing gradient i.e. from high to low grazing intensities as follows:

DECREASER SPECIES:	Grass & herbaceous species that decrease when veld is under or over grazed;
INCREASER I SPECIES:	Grass & herbaceous species that increase when veld is under grazed or selectively grazed;
INCREASER II SPECIES:	Grass & herbaceous species that increase when veld is over grazed.

- Based on experience, observation and local knowledge subjectively allocate forage and fuel factors on a scale of 0 - 10 according to the potential of the different grass species to produce forage for bulk grazers like cattle and fuel for supporting a surface fire. This procedure is used because it conforms to the concept of veld condition being the condition of the vegetation in relation to some functional characteristics and in this case the potential to produce grass forage and grass fuel.
- Using the information from above, develop a technique for assessing the condition of the grass sward based on the classification of the grass species into Decreaser and Increaser species together with their respective forage and fuel factors.
- Conduct grass surveys over the widest range of grassland, in as many different conditions as possible, and with these data statistically identify the key grass species that have the greatest positive and negative effect on veld condition in terms of their potential for producing forage. The potential for producing forage is calculated for each grass survey by multiplying the respective forage factors with the percentage relative frequency for each of the herbaceous plant species recorded during the different grass surveys. The sum of these products is expressed as the forage score for each sample site. The selection of the key grass species is done using a multiple regression analysis where the forage score is the dependent variable and the percentage frequency for each recorded grass or herbaceous species is the independent variable. The resultant regression model is then used for estimating the forage production potential of the veld at any sample site. Fuel scores are calculated in the same manner and are used in a multiple regression analysis for developing the regression model for estimating the fuel production potential of the veld at any sample site. The resultant regression models are tested statistically using data from additional independent grass surveys where the relationship between the predicted and observed forage and fuel scores is determined and statistically evaluated. Finally the data from the independent grass surveys are used to subjectively evaluate the outputs of the simplified key grass species technique for assessing veld condition according to the experience of local land owners.

The reason for selecting the key grass species in terms of their forage production potential is because the major portion of the Lüneburg area is used for livestock production and it is therefore essential that the key grass species be selected to reflect the grazing potential of the area. Experience has indicated that key forage species are also capable of reflecting the potential of other functional characteristics like grass fuel potential that involve some aspect of plant production.

Data collection for the above steps is relatively simple and easily recorded in the field.

The formulation of the Veld Management Program for the Lüneburg Agriculture and Conservation Demonstration Project was conducted using the following steps:

- Assessed the condition of the veld in each of the HVU's according to the procedure described by Trollope (1990).

This involved conducting a full species assessment of the botanical composition of the grass sward together with recording the basal cover represented by the point to tuft distance developed by Hardy & Tainton (1993):

- Using the full species data recorded during the assessment of the condition of the veld in the different HVU's developed a Key Species Technique for assessing veld condition using the procedure developed and described by Trollope (1990) in the Kruger National Park.

The resultant simplified technique will apply to all the veld types occurring in the Luneburg area.

- Based on the aforementioned assessment of the condition of the veld in the different HVU's formulate a veld management program comprising the most ecologically and economically appropriate Veld Management Practices, Systems and Layouts. The Veld Management Practices will include:
 - Stocking rates;
 - Grazing management;
 - Rotational resting;
 - Livestock ratios for cattle and sheep;
 - Prescribed burning.

Farmers wishing to establish the correct Veld Management Practices can be assisted by consulting the following literature sources:

- 2.5.1. *Veld and Pasture Management in South Africa, 1981.* (ed) N.M. Tainton. Shuter & Shooter, Pietermaritzburg. 251-261.
- 2.5.2. *Veld Management in the Eastern Cape, 1989.* (eds) J E Danckwerts & W R Teague. Govt. Printer, Pretoria.
- 2.5.3. Trollope, W.S.W., 1992. Chapter 3: Veld management in grassland and savanna areas. In: *Guide to grasses of South Africa.* (ed). F.P. van Oudtshoorn. Briza Publications, Arcadia , Pretoria: 45 -56.
- 2.5.4. *Veld Management In South Africa, 1999.* (ed). N.M. Tainton. University Natal Press, Pietermaritzburg. 412 - 422.

An example of a Veld Condition Assessment Form based on the above steps will be found below:

**VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland
MPUMALANGA PROVINCE**

Sample Site: GPS: S - Date:
Soil Type: E - RECORDER:

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>		14		11	
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>		6		5	
DECREASER TOTAL			*****		*****	
INCREASER I SPECIES	<i>Hyparrhenia species</i>		3		5	
	<i>Rendlia altera</i>		-4		1	
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>		3		5	
INCREASER I TOTAL			*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>		2		1	
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>		2		4	
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>		-6		-7	
	FORBS		-3		-2	
	BARE GROUND		-6		-7	
INCREASER II TOTAL			*****		*****	
OTHERS			CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100.0	TOTAL		TOTAL	
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 727x100% =						

CONCLUSIONS (tick appropriate block)								
1) VELD CONDITION				4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING			
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE Tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding?			
>600	Very High			HPG?	Vigour?			
501 – 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?			
401 – 500	Medium			REASON:		REASON:		
301 – 400	Low							
<301	Very Low							
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY				6) LIVESTOCK RATIO	7) TREND			
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall – 419.7)x 0.231)				Recommended = 1AU: 6 SSU	CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION	tick
GC = HA/AU				Current =AU:SSU	Decreaser		Correctly stocked	
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				COMMENT:	Increaser I		Under stocked	
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;					Increaser II		Over Stocked	
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increaser II		Selectively Grazed	
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall – mm.					COMMENT:			
3) STOCKING RATE								
Predicted =ha/AU								
Current =ha/AU								

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
	LOW	MOD	HIGH
Point To Tuft Distance	<4cm	4-5cm	>5cm
Distance – cm =			
Grass Standing Crop	LOW	HIGH	
	>1500kg/ha	<1500kg/ha	
kg/ha =			
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER			
INCREASER I			
INCREASER II			
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha =			
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

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GLOSSARY & INTERPRETATION OF VELD CONDITION SURVEYS FROM KEY SPECIES METHOD

i) VELD CONDITION

Veld Condition refers to the condition of the vegetation in relation to some functional characteristic (Trollope et al, 1990). In livestock production systems based on grassland vegetation the three most important functional characteristics are the forage and fuel production potential of the grass sward and its resistance to accelerated soil erosion.

ii) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (Vegetation Dependent)

Productivity of the grazeable portion of a homogeneous unit of vegetation expressed as the area of land required to maintain a single animal unit over an extended number of years without deterioration to vegetation or soil – ha/AU or AU/ha. Mean Grazing Capacity is estimated taking into account the Veld Condition Score (VCS) and the previous 12 months rainfall using the Grazing Capacity Model developed by Danckwerts (1981) viz.

$$\text{GRAZING CAPACITY} = 365 / (-31.159 + (1.433 * \text{VCS } \%)) + ((\text{Rainfall mm} - 419.7) \times 0.231)$$

WHERE:

GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares per Animal Unit – HA/AU;
VCS % = Veld Condition Score expressed as a percentage;
Rainfall mm = Previous 12 months rainfall expressed in millimeters

The Veld Condition Score is estimated using the formula:

$$\text{VCS } \% = (\text{Sample Forage Score} / \text{Benchmark Forage Score}) \times 100$$

iii) STOCKING RATE (Operator Dependent)

Stocking Rate refers to the area of land in the system of management which the operator has allocated to each animal unit in the system (Booyesen, 1967). Stocking rate has a major influence on animal performance, economic return to the farmer and the long term condition of the veld and is the most important veld management practice.

GUIDELINES: FOR STOCKING RATE

The formulation of stocking rates for grazing animals (cattle and sheep) is based on the mean grazing capacity of the veld. This is estimated by using the veld conditions score (VCS) in the formula presented by Trollope and Willis (1984) which describes the relationship between VCS and the mean grazing capacity.

$$\text{GC} = \frac{100 \times \text{GC.BM}}{\text{VCS}}$$

Where:

GC = mean grazing capacity;
GC.BM = mean grazing capacity of the benchmark;
VCS = veld condition score

iv) ROTATIONAL GRAZING

Rotational grazing is the successive occupation of camps by livestock during the year so that not all the veld is grazed simultaneously (Tainton, 1981). There are two forms of rotational grazing:

- High Production Grazing (HPG) – the occupation of a camp by grazing animals until **all the acceptable and desirable Decreaser grass species** have been grazed to a stage that will ensure rapid regrowth and a high production of forage;
- High Utilization Grazing (HUG) – the occupation of a camp by grazing animals until **all the grass species** have been heavily grazed.

The use of these different forms of rotational grazing depends upon the condition of the veld and specifically the dominance of the different categories of grass species i.e. Decreaser and increaser species. Of course besides applying the correct form of rotational grazing appropriate adjustment must also be made to the stocking rate.

GUIDELINES FOR ROTATIONAL GRAZING

- a) If grass sward is dominated by Increaser I and II species this indicates selective grazing and requires application of HUG to reduce Increaser I species and promote Decreaser species;
- b) If grass sward dominated by Increaser I species this indicates undergrazing and requires application of HUG to reduce Increaser I species and promote Decreaser species;
- c) If grass sward dominated by Increaser II species this indicates overgrazing and requires application of HPG to reduce Increaser II species and promote Decreaser species;
- d) If grass sward dominated by Decreaser species this indicates optimum grazing and requires application of HPG and HUG to maintain Decreaser species and prevent development of Increaser I and II species.

Decreaser species dominated veld

This is veld that is in ideal condition for livestock production. This veld condition can be maintained by applying HPG which will ensure the high production of good quality forage and excellent animal performance. This is because the preferred grass species are grazed according to their physiological requirements and the livestock allowed selecting a superior diet. However, it is necessary to periodically apply HUG to maintain the veld at the Decreaser stage in the grassland succession and prevent it from developing to the Increaser I stage. In the sour and mixed veld areas this should be done once a year and in the sweetveld areas once every three years.

Increaser I species dominated veld

This is veld that has either been understocked or selectively grazed. Both these practices allow the grassland succession to progress from the sub-climax decrease stage to the higher increaser I stage. In order to reverse the succession to the more desirable Decreaser stage it is necessary to apply HUG. This can be combined with veld burning or the feeding of nitrogen/protein licks so as to minimize the negative aspects of this form of rotational grazing on animal performance.

Increaser II species dominated veld

This is veld that has been overstocked and is being overgrazed and ecologically constitutes a reversal in the grassland succession from the Decreaser stage to the lower pioneer increaser II stage. This can be reversed by applying HPG where the less abundant but more competitive Decreaser species will be favoured and encouraged to increase and dominate the sward. This treatment will also ensure good animal performance.

Increaser I and II species dominated veld

This type of veld develops in situations where there are a few large camps in the grazing system and either continuous grazing or a very low form of rotational grazing is applied. Both result in selective grazing which encourages increaser I species. However, these two forms of grazing also result in the overgrazing of the Decreaser species in the sward because of the extended grazing periods. This allows the increaser II species to dominate in the spaces between the less acceptable and tufted increaser I species.

The condition of this type of veld can be improved by subdividing the large camps into a multi-camp system and applying a combination of HUG and HPG. The HUG can be combined with either veld burning or the feeding of nitrogen / protein licks as described earlier. However, this treatment should only be applied for a maximum period of two growing seasons after which HPG is used to encourage the Decreaser species. The HUG treatment will firstly severely defoliate the increaser I species, which are less tolerant to grazing, but the subsequent application of HPG will then encourage and improve the vigour of the Decreaser species when it is applied.

v) ROTATIONAL RESTING

Rotational resting of the grass sward is the successive withdrawal of veld from grazing on a rotational basis for specific purposes. The principle reasons for resting veld are seeding, restoration of vigour and providing a fodder reserve for periods of scarcity. Besides stocking rate, rotational resting is one of the most important and essential veld management practices.

GUIDELINES FOR ROTATIONAL RESTING

- i) If grass sward dominated by Increaser I and/or II species apply seeding rest to promote Decreaser species i.e. Jan/Jan rest to promote *Themeda triandra* (rooigras) if potential dominant species;
- ii) If grass sward dominated by Decreaser species apply a vigour and fodder reserve rest to promote productivity and provide forage for periods of scarcity i.e. July/July rest to allow full growing seasons growth to promote grass vigour and accumulation and provision of a fodder reserve at the end of winter;
- iii) General rule – Sourveld areas – rest ¼ of grazing area annually; Sweetveld areas – rest 1/3 of grazing area annually.

A seeding rest is applied when the Decreaser species have declined in the grass sward. It is, therefore, appropriate when either increaser I or II species are dominant but in practice is more important in veld that has been overstocked where there is a serious lack of decrease grass species and the basal cover of the sward is very poor. Generally the most widely applicable rest period to apply for veld in this condition is from January to January because it maximizes the production of seed by *Themeda triandra* (red grass) the most important and widely distributed Decreaser species in the veld.

Resting the veld to restore plant vigour is necessary under all veld conditions and is aimed at the Decreaser species. In the sweetveld areas this necessitates resting the veld for a full year so that the grass plants can grow to maturity at which stage they are still valuable forage for livestock. In mixed and Sourveld areas a shorter rest comprising the late summer and autumn period (January - April) is adequate for this purpose and reduces the extent to which the grass becomes mature and unacceptable to livestock.

A fodder reserve rest is necessary under all veld conditions but enjoys priority when the veld is in excellent condition and seed production is not important. It is intended to provide a fodder reserve for that time of the year when there is the greatest likelihood of a deficiency. In the summer rainfall area of southern Africa this is during late winter/early spring (August/September). In the sweetveld areas the most appropriate rest period for this purpose is from July to July while in the mixed and Sourveld areas from January to July. When applying these rests it is important to use HUG beforehand so as to ensure that only new nutritious forage is produced during the rest period.

vi) LIVESTOCK RATIOS

Livestock ratios refer to the ratio of bulk grazers to concentrate grazers. The selective grazing habit of domestic livestock is related to the grazing sequence in which these different classes of animals utilize the veld. Normally heavy bulk grazers (cattle) precede light concentrate grazers (sheep) thus preparing the pasture for use by the animals which follow.

GUIDELINES FOR LIVESTOCK RATIOS

- i) Sourveld areas - Ratio of cattle to sheep should not exceed 1AU to 6SSU (Danckwerts, 1989);
- ii) Sweetveld areas - Ratio of cattle to sheep should not exceed 1AU to 3SSU because in arid areas the veld is more susceptible to selective grazing.

vii) TREND

Trends in the condition of the veld are indicated by the percentage Decreaser and/or Increaser grass species present in the grass sward. Decreaser dominant veld indicates correct stocking rates, Increaser I dominated veld indicates under stocking whereas Increaser II dominated veld indicates over stocking or Increaser I and II dominated veld indicates selectively grazed veld. Negative trends can be reversed either by resting, changing the grazing management and/or by burning.

viii) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL

The Soil Erosion Potential is the potential of the veld to resist soil erosion and is influenced by the Basal Cover represented by the Point to Tuft Distance (measured in cm) and the Standing Crop of Grass (kg/ha) estimated with a Disc Pasture Meter.

ix) VELD BURNING

Veld burning is an important and often essential management practice in livestock production systems, particularly in Sourveld areas. There are two primary and valid reasons for burning veld:

- i) Remove moribund and/or unacceptable grass material;
- ii) Eradicate and/or prevent the encroachment of undesirable plants.

Burning is ecologically permissible if the veld is dominated by Decreaser and/or Increaser I grass species. Burning is not recommended if Increaser II grass species are dominant as the veld should be given an opportunity to progress to a higher stage of plant succession i.e. to improve from pioneer increaser II grass species to the more productive and palatable Decreaser species stage. Post-fire grazing management is very important as it has the greatest positive or negative effect on veld condition.

2.6 Photos

Digital photos taken of each site are provided in the site reports.

3. SITE SELECTION

3.1 Stratification and marking of Sites

The grassland monitoring sites are stratified in order to represent and reflect management on these grasslands. Sites are selected to be representative of the grassland or wetland ecotone area represented on these farming areas. In addition, grassland sites are selected to monitor non-grass herbaceous plant diversity. Site selection is based using these approaches:

- A Google Landsat image is used to identify major ecological units reflected as result of variation of geology, vegetation and topography (therefore different soils).
- Grassland monitoring sites should reflect different veld conditions and species richness, therefore overgrazed areas as well as under-utilized areas as well as areas with high grass species richness (15 or more species per survey site of 2500 m²) and of areas of low species richness.

Site accessibility is important in order to make results comparable and to make the fieldwork as practical possible.

The results should reflect ecological zones (crests, slopes or wetlands).

PLEASE NOTE: For this study area the sites possibly do not reflect representative homogeneous areas due to factors such as the economical constraint (limitation in funds and time available to increase the number of sites) and political considerations (to survey as much as possible farms in the study area).

4. GRASSLAND MONITORING, MANAGEMENT AND SCHEDULING

4.1. Background

With Lüneburg and Wakkerstroom grasslands one key objective by Enviropulse CC and Prof W.S.W. Trollope is to determine key grass species that will be used for the future interpretation and management of the grazing areas within Veld Type Gm 14 of Mucina and Rutherford (2006). Specific management recommendations for each farm are provided, which will include the best / optimum stocking rate and composition of the grazing spectrum as well as the best application of fire or resting to obtain optimum veld conditions whilst in the same time achieving best flora diversity.

4.2. Scope

A total of 20 grassland monitoring sites (of a total of 57 for the Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland, Veld Type Gm 14, which is the most common grassland area between Lüneburg and Wakkerstroom) are selected in the Lüneburg area to be representative of grasslands observed from a Google satellite image. Of these sites it is suggested that some will be reassessed on a yearly basis in order to determine veld condition trends and to link these to veld management recommendations given/applied.

4.3. Objectives

The overall objective is to manage for grassland within a moderate state or an optimum proportion of Decreaser grass species. Linked to this objective is to manage for grasslands with optimum water catchment ability or grasslands that would have minimum soil erodability. This would typically be grassland without the dominance of Ouhout (*Leucosidea sericea*), alien invasive species, or the encroachment of Bramble or other weeds. Therefore grassland not severely degraded or overgrazed with poor basal cover and an Increaser 2 dominated species composition. The objective would therefore be to manage for grassland with a high proportion of productive palatable species and good basal cover. Two extreme conditions therefore need to be avoided, over-rested moribund grassland on the one extreme, and overgrazed severely degraded or severely disturbed grassland on the other extreme. This can be achieved by management strategies such as burning (or not burning, depending on the veld condition) and grazing (or resting from grazing, depending on veld condition). Veld condition is monitored and corrective actions would need to be implemented where trend in condition needs to be reversed.

4.4. Scheduling

Grasslands should be monitored on a yearly basis and preferably at the same time each year. February/March is the best time of the year to assess the veld condition and flora diversity. It is recommended that the plant diversity surveys be scheduled for February or March in following years when flowering of the forbs are more likely after the rain has commenced.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Veld Condition

Veld condition is illustrated in the appended tables and also in the illustration below, showing veld condition scores (%) of all 20 survey sites.

Goedgevonden – Veld condition survey sites reflected overgrazing at three of the four sites.

Heteropogon contortus was dominant in all of the survey sites. This grass is an indicator of slightly overgrazed conditions when it occurs in high frequencies.

One site was well managed (indicated by the dominance of the Decreaser grass, *Themeda triandra*).

La Bella Esperanza – Veld condition survey sites reflected selectively grazed conditions at three of the four sites. This implies that both increaser 1 and 2 species dominated.

Hyparrhenia hirta (classified with the Increaser 1 species) dominated at most of the survey sites, together with *Tristachya leucothrix* (climax grass species) and *Eragrostis curvula* (indicator of overgrazing or disturbance) or forbs.

One site was well managed – dominated by *Themeda triandra*.

Paardeplaats – Veld condition at Paardeplaats is either selectively grazed or overgrazed, as reflected by the four survey sites.

Selectively grazed conditions were characterized by the dominance of both Increaser 1 and 2 species (*Hyparrhenia hirta* & *Eragrostis curvula*). Overgrazed conditions were typically either *Heteropogon contortus* or *Eragrostis curvula* dominated veld.

Zuurbron – Veld condition at Zuurbron is a mixture of overgrazed and under-utilized and well managed veld.

Overgrazed conditions were typically either *Heteropogon contortus* or *Eragrostis curvula* dominated veld.

A well managed area was dominated by *Themeda triandra* and an under-utilized area was dominated by *Tristachya leucothrix*.

Bergvliet – Veld condition at Bergvliet is overgrazed (as reflected at two of the sites) or selectively grazed (from one site).

Heteropogon contortus dominated at two sites, this grass species is indicating slightly overgrazed conditions.

One of the sites also had a dominance of *Aristida transvaalensis*. The selectively grazed site was characterized by having both Increaser 1 species (*Rendlia altera*) and Increaser 2 species (*Heteropogon contortus*) in abundance.

Grass tuft distances were good at all of the grassland sites, with some only 2cm, but mostly 3 or 4 cm.

5.2. Key Grasses

Grass species identified and determined as significant for the Luneburg grassland area are the following:

Andropogon appendiculatus

Eragrostis curvula

Heteropogon contortus

Hyparrhenia species (lumping all thatching grass species)

Rendlia altera

Themeda triandra and

Tristachya leucothrix

Dicotyledonous forbs were also included with the 7 grass species, together with bare ground.

These key plant species and bare ground appears in the Key Grass Table included in this report and forage and fuel values for these are also established.

Correlations between veld conditions from the full grass survey as reflected by the tables (appended in this report) are made with the results obtained from the Key Grass Species method (tables also appended). The results from these two methods correlate very well.

5.3. Flora Diversity

The plant diversity from flora surveys is illustrated in the graph below. No clear relationship is observed between veld condition and flora diversity.

5.4. Grazing Management

GOEDGEVONDEN

Grazing Capacity – productivity of the grazeable portion of a homogeneous unit of vegetation expressed as the area of land required to maintain a single animal unit over an extended number of years without deterioration to vegetation or soil – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990).

Stocking Rate – area of land in the system of management which the operator (farmer) has allotted to each animal unit in the system, and is expressed per length of the grazeable period of the year – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990);

The current stocking rate at Goedgevonden is 5.3 ha/AU².

Thus Stocking Rate is farmer dependent and Grazing Capacity is vegetation dependent and when formulating a stocking rate for a farm it is assumed that this should be based on the Mean Grazing Capacity of the farm as a whole for maintaining and/ or improving the condition of the veld. The Mean Grazing Capacity for a farm is estimated by calculating the mean Veld Condition Score for the different homogeneous vegetation units (HVU's) on the farm and using this value to estimate the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the farm. This value is then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for livestock on the farm. In the Lüneburg Project the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the different farms has been estimated by calculating the mean veld condition score for each property based on veld condition surveys that were conducted in the different homogeneous units that were demarcated on the farms. The resultant mean veld condition score was then used in the Grazing Capacity Model developed by Danckwerts (1981) together with a conservative estimate of the mean annual rainfall which in the case of Lüneburg was assumed to be 1000mm per annum. The resultant estimate of the Mean Grazing Capacity was then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for the livestock on the different farms. The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm *Goedgevonden* was formulated as follows – see in table below:

Veld Condition Survey	Veld Condition Score - %	Mean Annual Rainfall – mm p.a.	Grazing Capacity – ha/AU	Recommended Stocking Rate – ha/AU
Site 2	75.2	1000	1.7	-
Site 3A	45.4	1000	2.2	-
Site 3B	55.4	1000	2	-
Site 5	38.6	1000	2.3	-
Site 6	49.2	1000	2.1	-
Mean	52.8	1000	2.1	2.1

The mean grazing capacity for the farm Goedgevonden is therefore 2.1 ha/AU.

The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm Goedgevonden based on the Mean Grazing Capacity estimated from the mean veld condition scores that are obtained from veld condition surveys conducted in five homogeneous vegetation units and assuming a conservative mean annual rainfall of 1000mm p.a.

Livestock Ratio:

The ratio for livestock should be in the order of 1 large stock unit (1 LAU) to 6 small stock units (SSU), where large stock units are represented by bulk feeders (i.e. cattle = 1 large animal unit) and small stock units by concentrate/selective feeders (i.e. sheep as represented by 1 sheep = 1 small stock unit). If the ratio exceeds this 1:6 ratio (i.e. 1:7 or larger) there will be a definite risk to selective grazing.

Livestock ratio of bulk grazers (cattle) to concentrate grazers (sheep and blesbuck) is 1: 2.4 which is desirable and will minimize the potential for selective grazing

² PLEASE NOTE:

- This information is sourced from an interview with the farmer / manager. However, the current veld condition trend is unknown, for past management may have lead to overgrazed conditions that could still be reflected from current veld condition assessments. However, regular veld condition assessments will confirm if the veld condition is improving or not (i.e. will establish the veld condition trend).
- Another possibility to explain the difference between the current stocking rate and the current veld condition is that the survey sites or the quantity of sites stratified do not truly reflect the current grazing scenario or veld condition - hence more representative sites are required to truly reflect the veld condition in this instant in time. However, there was a restraint due to the economical situation (limit in budget and time) and politics (more than one farm had to be surveyed).

LA BELLA ESPERANZA

Grazing Capacity – productivity of the grazeable portion of a homogeneous unit of vegetation expressed as the area of land required to maintain a single animal unit over an extended number of years without deterioration to vegetation or soil – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990).

Stocking Rate – area of land in the system of management which the operator (farmer) has allotted to each animal unit in the system, and is expressed per length of the grazeable period of the year – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990);

The current stocking rate at La Bella Esperanza is 4.3 ha/AU³.

Thus *Stocking Rate* is farmer dependent and *Grazing Capacity* is vegetation dependent and when formulating a stocking rate for a farm it is assumed that this should be based on the Mean Grazing Capacity of the farm as a whole for maintaining and/ or improving the condition of the veld. The Mean Grazing Capacity for a farm is estimated by calculating the mean Veld Condition Score for the different homogeneous vegetation units (HVU's) on the farm and using this value to estimate the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the farm. This value is then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for livestock on the farm. In the Lüneburg Project the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the different farms has been estimated by calculating the mean veld condition score for each property based on veld condition surveys that were conducted in the different homogeneous units that were demarcated on the farms. The resultant mean veld condition score was then used in the Grazing Capacity Model developed by Danckwerts (1981) together with a conservative estimate of the mean annual rainfall which in the case of Lüneburg was assumed to be 1000mm per annum. The resultant estimate of the Mean Grazing Capacity was then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for the livestock on the different farms. The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm *La Bella Esperanza* was formulated as follows – see in table below:

Veld Condition Survey	Veld Condition Score - %	Mean Annual Rainfall – mm p.a.	Grazing Capacity – ha/AU	Recommended Stocking Rate – ha/AU
Site 6	38.1	1000	2.3	-
Site 7	43.0	1000	2.2	-
Site 8	35.0	1000	2.4	-
Site 9	52.3	1000	2.1	-
Mean	42.1	1000	2.2	2.2

The mean grazing capacity for the farm La Bella Esperanza is therefore 2.2 ha/AU.

The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm La Bella Esperanza based on the Mean Grazing Capacity estimated from the mean veld condition scores that are obtained from veld condition surveys conducted in four homogeneous vegetation units and assuming a conservative mean annual rainfall of 1000mm p.a.

Livestock Ratio:

The ratio for livestock should be in the order of 1 large stock unit (1 LAU) to 6 small stock units (SSU), where large stock units are represented by bulk feeders (i.e. cattle = 1 large animal unit) and small stock units by concentrate/selective feeders (i.e. sheep as represented by 1 sheep = 1 small stock unit). If the ratio exceeds this 1:6 ratio (i.e. 1:7 or larger) there will be a definite risk to selective grazing.

Livestock ratio of bulk grazers (cattle) to concentrate grazers (sheep) is 1: 2.5 which is desirable and will minimize the potential for selective grazing.

³ This information is sourced from an interview with the farmer / manager. However, the current veld condition trend is unknown, for past management may have lead to overgrazed conditions that could still be reflected from current veld condition assessments. However, regular veld condition assessments will confirm if the veld condition is improving or not (i.e. will establish the veld condition trend).

Another possibility to explain the difference between the current stocking rate and the current veld condition is that the survey sites or the quantity of sites stratified do not truly reflect the current grazing scenario or veld condition - hence more representative sites are required to truly reflect the veld condition in this instant in time. However, there was a restraint due to the economical situation (limit in budget and time) and politics (more than one farm had to be surveyed).

PAARDEPLAATS

Grazing Capacity – productivity of the grazeable portion of a homogeneous unit of vegetation expressed as the area of land required to maintain a single animal unit over an extended number of years without deterioration to vegetation or soil – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990).

Stocking Rate – area of land in the system of management which the operator (farmer) has allotted to each animal unit in the system, and is expressed per length of the grazeable period of the year – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990);

The current stocking rate at Paardeplaats is 3.8 ha/AU⁴.

Thus *Stocking Rate* is farmer dependent and *Grazing Capacity* is vegetation dependent and when formulating a stocking rate for a farm it is assumed that this should be based on the Mean Grazing Capacity of the farm as a whole for maintaining and/ or improving the condition of the veld. The Mean Grazing Capacity for a farm is estimated by calculating the mean Veld Condition Score for the different homogeneous vegetation units (HVU's) on the farm and using this value to estimate the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the farm. This value is then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for livestock on the farm.

In the Lüneburg Project the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the different farms has been estimated by calculating the mean veld condition score for each property based on veld condition surveys that were conducted in the different homogeneous units that were demarcated on the farms. The resultant mean veld condition score was then used in the Grazing Capacity Model developed by Danckwerts (1981) together with a conservative estimate of the mean annual rainfall which in the case of Lüneburg was assumed to be 1000mm per annum. The resultant estimate of the Mean Grazing Capacity was then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for the livestock on the different farms. The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm *Paardeplaats* was formulated as follows – see in table below:

Veld Condition Survey	Veld Condition Score - %	Mean Annual Rainfall – mm p.a.	Grazing Capacity – ha/AU	Recommended Stocking Rate – ha/AU
Site 1A	51.4	1000	2.1	-
Site 1B	51.7	1000	2.1	-
Site 2	54.8	1000	2.0	-
Site 4	46.8	1000	2.1	-
Mean	51.2	1000	2.1	2.1

The mean grazing capacity for the farm Paardeplaats is therefore 2.1 ha/AU.

The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm Paardeplaats based on the Mean Grazing Capacity estimated from the mean veld condition scores that are obtained from veld condition surveys conducted in four homogeneous vegetation units and assuming a conservative mean annual rainfall of 1000mm p.a.

Livestock Ratio:

The ratio for livestock should be in the order of 1 large stock unit (1 LAU) to 6 small stock units (SSU), where large stock units are represented by bulk feeders (i.e. cattle = 1 large animal unit) and small stock units by concentrate/selective feeders (i.e. sheep as represented by 1 sheep = 1 small stock unit). If the ratio exceeds this 1:6 ratio (i.e. 1:7 or larger) there will be a definite risk to selective grazing.

Livestock ratio of bulk grazers (cattle) to concentrate grazers (sheep and blesbuck) is 1: 43 which is desirable and will minimize the potential for selective grazing.

⁴ This information is sourced from an interview with the farmer / manager. However, the current veld condition trend is unknown, for past management may have lead to overgrazed conditions that could still be reflected from current veld condition assessments. However, regular veld condition assessments will confirm if the veld condition is improving or not (i.e. will establish the veld condition trend).

Another possibility to explain the difference between the current stocking rate and the current veld condition is that the survey sites or the quantity of sites stratified do not truly reflect the current grazing scenario or veld condition - hence more representative sites are required to truly reflect the veld condition in this instant in time. However, there was a restraint due to the economical situation (limit in budget and time) and politics (more than one farm had to be surveyed).

ZUURBRON

Grazing Capacity – productivity of the grazeable portion of a homogeneous unit of vegetation expressed as the area of land required to maintain a single animal unit over an extended number of years without deterioration to vegetation or soil – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990).

Stocking Rate – area of land in the system of management which the operator (farmer) has allotted to each animal unit in the system, and is expressed per length of the grazeable period of the year – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990);

The current stocking rate at Zuurbron is 7.9 ha/AU⁵.

Thus Stocking Rate is farmer dependent and Grazing Capacity is vegetation dependent and when formulating a stocking rate for a farm it is assumed that this should be based on the Mean Grazing Capacity of the farm as a whole for maintaining and/ or improving the condition of the veld. The Mean Grazing Capacity for a farm is estimated by calculating the mean Veld Condition Score for the different homogeneous vegetation units (HVU's) on the farm and using this value to estimate the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the farm. This value is then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for livestock on the farm.

In the Lüneburg Project the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the different farms has been estimated by calculating the mean veld condition score for each property based on veld condition surveys that were conducted in the different homogeneous units that were demarcated on the farms.

The resultant mean veld condition score was then used in the Grazing Capacity Model developed by Danckwerts (1981) together with a conservative estimate of the mean annual rainfall which in the case of Lüneburg was assumed to be 1000mm per annum. The resultant estimate of the Mean Grazing Capacity was then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for the livestock on the different farms. The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm *Zuurbron* was formulated as follows – see in table below:

Veld Condition Survey	Veld Condition Score - %	Mean Annual Rainfall – mm p.a.	Grazing Capacity – ha/AU	Recommended Stocking Rate – ha/AU
Site 3A	46.6	1000	2.2	-
Site 6	47.5	1000	2.1	-
Site 7	70.4	1000	1.8	-
Site 8	36.5	1000	2.4	-
Mean	50.3	1000	2.1	2.1

The mean grazing capacity for the farm Zuurbron is therefore 2.1 ha/AU.

The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm Zuurbron based on the Mean Grazing Capacity estimated from the mean veld condition scores that are obtained from veld condition surveys conducted in four homogeneous vegetation units and assuming a conservative mean annual rainfall of 1000mm p.a.

Livestock Ratio:

It is recommended that the livestock be in the ratio of 1 large stock unit (1 LAU) to 6 small stock units (SSU), where large stock units are represented by bulk feeders (i.e. cattle = 1 large animal unit) and small stock units by concentrate/selective feeders (i.e. sheep as represented by 1 sheep = 1 small stock unit). If the ratio exceeds this 1:6 ratio (i.e. 1:7 or larger) there will be a definite risk to selective grazing.

Livestock ratio of bulk grazers (cattle) to concentrate grazers (sheep) is 1: 69 which is not desirable and will influence the potential for selective grazing.

⁵ This information is sourced from an interview with the farmer / manager. However, the current veld condition trend is unknown, for past management may have lead to overgrazed conditions that could still be reflected from current veld condition assessments. However, regular veld condition assessments will confirm if the veld condition is improving or not (i.e. will establish the veld condition trend).

Another possibility to explain the difference between the current stocking rate and the current veld condition is that the survey sites or the quantity of sites stratified do not truly reflect the current grazing scenario or veld condition - hence more representative sites are required to truly reflect the veld condition in this instant in time. However, there was a restraint due to the economical situation (limit in budget and time) and politics (more than one farm had to be surveyed).

BERGVLIET

Grazing Capacity – productivity of the grazeable portion of a homogeneous unit of vegetation expressed as the area of land required to maintain a single animal unit over an extended number of years without deterioration to vegetation or soil – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990).

Stocking Rate – area of land in the system of management which the operator (farmer) has allotted to each animal unit in the system, and is expressed per length of the grazeable period of the year – ha/AU (Trollope, Trollope & Bosch, 1990);

The current stocking rate at Bergvliet is 3.3 ha/AU⁶.

Thus *Stocking Rate* is farmer dependent and *Grazing Capacity* is vegetation dependent and when formulating a stocking rate for a farm it is assumed that this should be based on the Mean Grazing Capacity of the farm as a whole for maintaining and/ or improving the condition of the veld. The Mean Grazing Capacity for a farm is estimated by calculating the mean Veld Condition Score for the different homogeneous vegetation units (HVU's) on the farm and using this value to estimate the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the farm. This value is then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for livestock on the farm.

In the Lüneburg Project the Mean Grazing Capacity of the veld on the different farms has been estimated by calculating the mean veld condition score for each property based on veld condition surveys that were conducted in the different homogeneous units that were demarcated on the farms. The resultant mean veld condition score was then used in the Grazing Capacity Model developed by Danckwerts (1981) together with a conservative estimate of the mean annual rainfall which in the case of Lüneburg was assumed to be 1000mm per annum.

The resultant estimate of the Mean Grazing Capacity was then used as the recommended Stocking Rate for the livestock on the different farms. The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm *Bergvliet* was formulated as follows – see in table below:

Veld Condition Survey	Veld Condition Score - %	Mean Annual Rainfall – mm p.a.	Grazing Capacity – ha/AU	Recommended Stocking Rate – ha/AU
Site 1	53.3	1000	2.0	-
Site 2	28.0	1000	2.6	-
Site 3	30.4	1000	2.5	-
Mean	37.2	1000	2.4	2.4

The mean grazing capacity for the farm Bergvliet is therefore 2.4 ha/AU.

The recommended Stocking Rate for the farm Bergvliet based on the Mean Grazing Capacity estimated from the mean veld condition scores that are obtained from veld condition surveys conducted in three homogeneous vegetation units and assuming a conservative mean annual rainfall of 1000mm p.a.

Livestock Ratio:

The ratio for livestock should be in the order of 1 large stock unit (1 LAU) to 6 small stock units (SSU), where large stock units are represented by bulk feeders (i.e. cattle = 1 large animal unit) and small stock units by concentrate/selective feeders (i.e. sheep as represented by 1 sheep = 1 small stock unit). If the ratio exceeds this 1:6 ratio (i.e. 1:7 or larger) there will be a definite risk to selective grazing.

Livestock ratio of bulk grazers (cattle) to concentrate grazers (sheep or blesbuck) is 1: 4.1 which is desirable and will minimize the potential for selective grazing.

⁶ This information is sourced from an interview with the farmer / manager. However, the current veld condition trend is unknown, for past management may have lead to overgrazed conditions that could still be reflected from current veld condition assessments. However, regular veld condition assessments will confirm if the veld condition is improving or not (i.e. will establish the veld condition trend).

Another possibility to explain the difference between the current stocking rate and the current veld condition is that the survey sites or the quantity of sites stratified do not truly reflect the current grazing scenario or veld condition - hence more representative sites are required to truly reflect the veld condition in this instant in time. However, there was a restraint due to the economical situation (limit in budget and time) and politics (more than one farm had to be surveyed).

6. SUMMARY

The general impression from the survey sites (which were selected as representative points of veld conditions at the Lüneburg farms) is that selective grazing occurs in some areas, overgrazing in others, with well managed or over-rested conditions also present.

Although it was not economically feasible to survey more sites within the available time the question may be asked how representative these sites are of the vegetation observed within the Lüneburg area. However, due to political constraints the sampling density was spread out between a few farms even though all 20 sites on one farm would have been more realistic to present homogenous units present on the farm.

From the Key Grass Species assessments current grazing capacity was established per farm. The grazing capacity was mostly 2.1 ha/AU but more conservative figures were 2.2 and 2.4 ha/AU.

Current stocking rates of all the farms are below the recommended stocking rates. Veld conditions do not correlate with the current numbers of livestock present in this instant in time. It is possible that the grassland areas are still in a trend of recovering from historical overgrazing or that more survey sites would reflect the current conditions created by current livestock management.

The livestock ratios were mostly correct with minor adjustments at one farm where the ratio between cattle and sheep exceeds the recommended 1:6 ratio. Specific grazing management recommendations are made per survey site within Key Grass tables.

The application of fire in terms of the season of burning (autumn burns) on its own should not be seen as detrimental or beneficial for the grazing without qualifying the type of management, i.e. grazing or rest, directly after the burn is applied. Some autumn burns are followed by 18 months rest (protection from grazing) but with other farms these areas are continuously grazed for a year after the burn (after which the camp is rested for the following year). However, veld conditions appear to be better in areas where it is not continuously grazed for 11 months after the fire.

Plant species diversity was generally reasonable or poor, but never excellent. A few sites had Red Data plant species present.

7. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

A special word of thanks to Horst and Rona Filter: excellent arrangements with the workshops and hospitality during the fieldwork period.

Also to Prof Winston and Lynn Trollope for their hospitality and their significant contribution with key grasses and grazing management presented in this report with the site specific recommendations in the key grass species attachments.

8. REFERENCES

- BOSCH, O. J. H. 1989.** Degradation of the semi-arid grasslands of southern Africa. *Journal of Arid Environments* (1989) 16, 165-175
- COLWELL, R.K. 2005.** EstimateS: Statistical estimation of species richness and shared species from samples. Version 7.5. User's Guide and application published at: <http://purl.oclc.org/estimates>.
- DANKWERTS, J.E., 1981.** A technique to assess the grazing capacity of sweetveld with particular reference to the False Thornveld areas of the Ciskei. MSc Thesis, Dept. Pasture Science, Univ. Natal, Pietermaritzburg, South Africa: 1-245.
- HARDY, M.B & TAINTON, N.M., 1993.** Towards a technique for determining basal cover in tufted grasslands. *Afr. J. Range & For. Sci* 10(2): 77-81.
- MUCINA, L & RUTHERFORD, C. 2006.** The Vegetation of South Africa, Lesotho and Swaziland. *Strelitzia* 19: 807 pp.
- TAINTON, N.M. 1988.** Veld and Pasture Management in South Africa. Shuter & Shooter, Pietermaritzburg. 481 pp.
- TAINTON, N.M. 1999.** Veld Management in South Africa. University of Natal Press, Pietermaritzburg. 472 pp.
- TROLLOPE, W S W., 1990.** Development of a technique for assessing veld condition in the Kruger National Park. *J. Grassld. Soc. South. Afr.* 7, 1:46-51.
- TROLLOPE, W.S.W. & POTGIETER, A. 1986.** Estimating Grass Fuel Loads With A Disc Meter In The Kruger National Park – *J. Grassl. Soc. Sth. Afr.* 3,4:148-152.
- TROLLOPE, W S W, TROLLOPE, L.A. & BOSCH, O J H., 1990.** Veld and pasture management terminology in Southern Africa. *J. Grassld. Soc. South Afr.* 7,1:52-61.

APPENDIX A

MAPS

Goedgevonden 134 HT

Legend

- Survey Sites
- Contours (20m Interval)
- Roads
- Dams
- Rivers
- Goedgevonden 134 HT Stratification

EMROSS Consulting (Pty) Ltd

P.O. Box 507
White River
1240

e-mail: a.emery@emross.co.za

La Belle Esperance 191 HT

Paardeplaats 101 HT

Legend

- Survey Sites
- Contours (20m Interval)
- Roads
- Dams
- Rivers
- Paardeplaats 101 HT Stratification

0 0.5 1 2 3 Kilometers

EMROSS Consulting (Pty) Ltd

P.O. Box 507
White River
1240

e-mail: a.emery@emross.co.za

Zuurbron 132 HT

Legend

- Survey Sites
- Contours (20m Interval)
- Roads
- Dams
- Rivers
- Zuurbron 132 HT Stratification

EMROSS Consulting (Pty) Ltd

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Bergvliet 192 HT

Legend

- Survey Sites
- ~ Contours (20m Interval)
- Roads
- ☞ Dams
- ~ Rivers
- 🔴 Bergvliet 192 HT Stratification

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APPENDIX B

LUNEBURG VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORTS

**VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORTS
GOEDGEVONDEN**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009
(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, Goedgevonden	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 2	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 17' 46.0"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 28' 48.9"	
Height above sea level	1620m	
Position in landscape	Midslope/ Wetland Ecotone	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite – Sandy Clay	
Date visited	12/02/2009	
Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)	5171 kg/ha = Very High	
Organic accumulation	2 = Low	
Number of Grass species	16 species = Medium	
Number of Forbs species	31 species = Medium	
Non-grass species diversity	1.83 = Low	
Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	668 / Very high	
Water Catchment Potential	3 cm = High	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	9% = Within expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Well Managed 66.8%	

12/02/2009

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score</p> <p><small>>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</small></p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition</p> <p>Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Goedgevonden</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 3a</p> <p>S 27° 17' 15.9"</p> <p>E 30° 28' 25.5"</p> <p>1661m</p> <p>Crest</p> <p>Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam</p> <p>12/02/2009</p> <p>3222 kg/ha = High</p> <p>1 = Low</p> <p>15 species = Reasonable</p> <p>17 species = low</p> <p>1.95 = low</p> <p>403 / Moderate</p> <p>2 cm = high</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>9% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Overgrazed</p> <p>45.5%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">12/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Lunenburg, Goedgevonden	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 3b	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 16' 44.3"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 28' 46.5"	
Height above sea level	1635m	
Position in landscape	Crest	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite / Glenrosa	
Date visited	12/02/2009	
Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)	3260 kg/ha = High	
Organic accumulation	2 = Low	
Number of Grass species	17 species = Medium	
Number of Forbs species	28 species = Low	
Non-grass species diversity	2.24 = Medium	
Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	492 / Moderate	
Water Catchment Potential	3 cm = High	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	14% = Slightly exceeding expected norms	
Veld Condition	Overgrazed	
Assessment / VC Score %	55.4%	12/02/2009

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score</p> <p><small>>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</small></p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition</p> <p>Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Lunenburg, Goedgevonden</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 5</p> <p>S 27° 17' 40.6"</p> <p>E 30° 28' 51.5"</p> <p>1615m</p> <p>Midslope</p> <p>Dolerite / Mispah</p> <p>11/02/2009</p> <p>2500 kg/ha = Medium</p> <p>1 = Low</p> <p>11 species = Medium</p> <p>31 species = Medium</p> <p>2.45 = Medium</p> <p>343 / Low</p> <p>2 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>4% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Overgrazed</p> <p>34.3%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">11/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score</p> <p><small>>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</small></p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition</p> <p>Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Goedgevonden</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 6</p> <p>S 27° 18' 06.1"</p> <p>E 30° 29' 23.4"</p> <p>1648m</p> <p>Midslope</p> <p>Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam</p> <p>24/02/2009</p> <p>4500 kg/ha = Very High</p> <p>2 = Low</p> <p>12 species = Medium</p> <p>21 species = Low</p> <p>1.94 = Low</p> <p>437 / Moderate</p> <p>3 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>6% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Overgrazed</p> <p>49.2%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">24/02/2009</p>
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**VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORTS
LA BELLA ESPERANZA**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, La Belle Esperanza	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 6	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 16' 47.2"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 34' 31.4"	
Height above sea level	1313m	
Position in landscape	Crest	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam	
Date visited	12/02/2009	
Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)	6159 kg/ha = Very High	
Organic accumulation	3 = Medium	
Number of Grass species	17 species = Medium	
Number of Forbs species	27 species = Low	
Non-grass species diversity	2.43 = Medium	
Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	338 / Low	
Water Catchment Potential	4 cm = High	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	19% = Slightly exceeding expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Selectively grazed 38.1%	

12/02/2009

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, La Bella Esperanza	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 7	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 17' 48.7"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 32' 14.8"	
Height above sea level	1611m	
Position in landscape	Crest	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam	
Date visited	17/02/2009	
Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)	3325 kg/ha = High	
Organic accumulation	2 = Low	
Number of Grass species	23 species = High	
Number of Forbs species	19 species = Low	
Non-grass species diversity	2.07 = Medium	
Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	382 / Low	
Water Catchment Potential	4 cm = High	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	17% = Slightly exceeding expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Selectively grazed 43.0%	

17/02/2009

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, La Belle Esperanza	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 8	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 17' 07.8"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 33' 07.8"	
Height above sea level	1384m	
Position in landscape	Midslope	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam	
Date visited	17/02/2009	
Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)	6861 kg/ha = Very High	
Organic accumulation	4 = High	
Number of Grass species	8 species = Low	
Number of Forbs species	21 species = Low	
Non-grass species diversity	2.2 = Medium	
Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	311 / Low	
Water Catchment Potential	5 cm = Medium	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	30% = Exceeding expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Selectively grazed 35.0%	

17/02/2009

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p>	<p>Luneburg, La Belle Esperanza</p>	
<p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p>	<p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p>	
<p>Site number</p>	<p>Site 9</p>	
<p>Latitude (S)</p>	<p>S 27° 17' 38.4"</p>	
<p>Longitude (E)</p>	<p>E 30° 33' 04.4"</p>	
<p>Height above sea level</p>	<p>1428m</p>	
<p>Position in landscape</p>	<p>Midslope</p>	
<p>Geology/Soils</p>	<p>Dolerite / Glenrosa & Mispah</p>	
<p>Date visited</p>	<p>17/02/2009</p>	
<p>Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)</p>	<p>4384 kg/ha = Very High</p>	
<p>Organic accumulation</p>	<p>2 = Low</p>	
<p>Number of Grass species</p>	<p>21 species = high</p>	
<p>Number of Forbs species</p>	<p>18 species = low</p>	
<p>Non-grass species diversity</p>	<p>2.21 = medium</p>	
<p>Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</p>	<p>464 / Moderate</p>	
<p>Water Catchment Potential</p>	<p>3 cm = high</p>	
<p>Bare Ground</p>	<p>0% recorded</p>	
<p>Forbs Abundance</p>	<p>7% = Within expected norms</p>	
<p>Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Well Managed 52.3%</p>	

17/02/2009

**VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORTS
PAARDEPLAATS**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Paardeplaats</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 1a</p> <p>S 27° 15' 36.0"</p> <p>E 30° 28' 30.9"</p> <p>1679m</p> <p>Crest /Midslope</p> <p>Dolerite / Glenrosa</p> <p>18/02/2009</p> <p>3472 kg/ha = High</p> <p>2 = Low</p> <p>11 species = Medium</p> <p>22 species = Low</p> <p>2.10 = Medium</p> <p>456 / Moderate</p> <p>4 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>17% = Slightly exceeding expected norms</p> <p>Selectively grazed</p> <p>51.4%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">18/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition</p> <p>Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Paardeplaats</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 1b</p> <p>S 27° 15' 06.1"</p> <p>E 30° 28' 07.2"</p> <p>1693m</p> <p>Crest</p> <p>Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam</p> <p>18/02/2009</p> <p>3858 kg/ha = High</p> <p>1 = Low</p> <p>10 species = Medium</p> <p>20 species = Low</p> <p>1.64 = Low</p> <p>459 / Moderate</p> <p>3 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>6% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Overgrazed</p> <p>51.7%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">18/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, Paardeplaats	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 2	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 15' 25.8"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 28' 40.8"	
Height above sea level	1669m	
Position in landscape	Crest	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam	
Date visited	18/02/2009	
Fuel load	2939 kg/ha = Medium	
Organic accumulation	1 = Low	
Number of Grass species	10 species = Medium	
Number of Forbs species	18 species = Low	
Non-grass species diversity	2.17 = Medium	
Forage Score <small>>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</small>	487 / Moderate	
Water Catchment Potential	3 cm = High	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	11% = Within expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Overgrazed 54.8%	

18/02/2009

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, Paardeplaats	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 4	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 16' 40.1"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 28' 42.1"	
Height above sea level	1628m	
Position in landscape	Rocky Crest	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite / Mispah & Glenrosa	
Date visited	18/02/2009	
Fuel load	1732 kg/ha = Low	
Organic accumulation	1 = Low	
Number of Grass species	8 species = Low	
Number of Forbs species	14 species = Low	
Non-grass species diversity	1.78 = Low	
Forage Score <small>>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</small>	416 / Moderate	
Water Catchment Potential	2cm = High	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	7% = Within expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Selectively grazed 46.8 %	

18/02/2009

**VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORTS
ZUURBRON**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, Zuurbron	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Relief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 3a	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 17' 25.3"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 27' 21.2"	
Height above sea level	1666m	
Position in landscape	Midslope	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam	
Date visited	24/02/2009	
Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)	2290 kg/ha = Medium	
Organic accumulation	1 = Low	
Number of Grass species	14 species = Medium	
Number of Forbs species	32 species = Medium	
Non-grass species diversity	2.38 = Medium	
Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	414 / Moderate	
Water Catchment Potential	3 cm = high	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	9% = Within expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Overgrazed 46.6%	

24/02/2009

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Zuurbron</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 6</p> <p>S 27° 18' 03.9"</p> <p>E 30° 25' 57.2"</p> <p>1670m</p> <p>Midslope</p> <p>Sandstone - Sandy</p> <p>24/02/2009</p> <p>3787 kg/ha = High</p> <p>2 = Low</p> <p>13 species = Medium</p> <p>14 species = Low</p> <p>1.02 = Low</p> <p>422 / Moderate</p> <p>3 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>3% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Overgrazed</p> <p>47.5%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">24/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009 (Zuurbron, Site 6)

- Trends in Condition – from Grasses

Protect against fire in 2009.

- Trends in Condition – from Non-grass herbaceous forbs

Protect against fire in 2009.

Notes

- The water catchment ability is high.
- A medium number of grass species is recorded.
- There is a low number of forb species.
- The forb species diversity is 1.02, which is low (Shannon Mean of >3.0 is considered high – 4.5 very high).
- The veld condition is overgrazed.
- The grass fuel load or grazing volume is high.
- The organic accumulation is low.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Zuurbron</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 7</p> <p>S 27° 16' 43.7"</p> <p>E 30° 25' 41.6"</p> <p>1735m</p> <p>Midslope</p> <p>Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam</p> <p>25/02/2009</p> <p>4234 kg/ha = Very High</p> <p>1 = Low</p> <p>13 species = Medium</p> <p>27 species = Low</p> <p>2.46 = Medium</p> <p>625 / Very high</p> <p>2 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>9% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Well Managed</p> <p>70.4%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">25/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

Area / Farm	Luneburg, Zuurbron	
Veld Type (Acocks)	Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld	
Site number	Site 8	
Latitude (S)	S 27° 17' 44.3"	
Longitude (E)	E 30° 26' 38.4"	
Height above sea level	1673m	
Position in landscape	Midslope	
Geology/Soils	Dolerite / Mispah & Glenrosa	
Date visited	25/02/2009	
Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)	4016 kg/ha = Very High	
Organic accumulation	2 = Low	
Number of Grass species	24 species = Good	
Number of Forbs species	18 species = Low	
Non-grass species diversity	1.55 = Low	
Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	324 / Low	
Water Catchment Potential	3 cm = High	
Bare Ground	0% recorded	
Forbs Abundance	11% = Within expected norms	
Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %	Over-rested 36.5%	

25/02/2009

**VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORTS
BERGVLIET**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score</p> <p><small>>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</small></p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Bergvliet</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 1</p> <p>S 27° 17' 50.3"</p> <p>E 30° 30' 08.4"</p> <p>1634m</p> <p>Crest</p> <p>Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam</p> <p>23/02/2009</p> <p>2876 kg/ha = Medium</p> <p>2 = Low</p> <p>9 species = Low</p> <p>14 species = Low</p> <p>1.68 = Low</p> <p>473 / Moderate</p> <p>3 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>9% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Overgrazed / 53.3%</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">23/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Bergvliet</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 2</p> <p>S 27° 17' 20.4"</p> <p>E 30° 30' 42.9"</p> <p>1614m</p> <p>Crest / Midslope</p> <p>Dolerite / Mispah</p> <p>24/02/2009</p> <p>2213 kg/ha = Medium</p> <p>2 = Low</p> <p>19 species = Medium</p> <p>23 species = Low</p> <p>1.98 = Low</p> <p>249 / Very low</p> <p>3 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>6% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Overgrazed</p> <p>28.0%</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">24/02/2009</p>
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VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT REPORT – 2009

(SEE ATTACHED TABLE)

<p>Area / Farm</p> <p>Veld Type (Acocks)</p> <p>Site number</p> <p>Latitude (S)</p> <p>Longitude (E)</p> <p>Height above sea level</p> <p>Position in landscape</p> <p>Geology/Soils</p> <p>Date visited</p> <p>Fuel load (3 tons/ha threshold for burning climax or selectively grazed areas; 4 tons/ha for other areas, including wetland ecotones)</p> <p>Organic accumulation</p> <p>Number of Grass species</p> <p>Number of Forbs species</p> <p>Non-grass species diversity</p> <p>Forage Score >600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low</p> <p>Water Catchment Potential</p> <p>Bare Ground</p> <p>Forbs Abundance</p> <p>Veld Condition Assessment / VC Score %</p>	<p>Luneburg, Bergvliet</p> <p>Veld Type 63 – Piet Retief Sourveld</p> <p>Site 3</p> <p>S 27° 17' 32.2"</p> <p>E 30° 30' 45.6"</p> <p>1628m</p> <p>Crest</p> <p>Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam</p> <p>23/02/2009</p> <p>5090 kg/ha = Very High</p> <p>1 = Low</p> <p>12 species = Medium</p> <p>17 species = Low</p> <p>1.84 = Low</p> <p>270 / Very low</p> <p>3 cm = High</p> <p>0% recorded</p> <p>4% = Within expected norms</p> <p>Selectively grazed</p> <p>30.4%</p>	<p style="text-align: right;">23/02/2009</p>
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APPENDIX C

LUNEBURG TABLES

**GRASS SPECIES TABLES – FULL SURVEYS
GOEDGEVONDEN**

Table 1.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG GOEDGEVONDEN	MIDSLOPE / WETLAND ECOTONE	
	Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 2	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	5171	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 46.0"	
East	30° 28' 48.9"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1620	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	130°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i> Vlei Bluestem / Vleiblougras	2	2
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	3	3
<i>Monocymbium cerasiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	**	**
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	44	51
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	49	56
INCREASES I		
<i>Digitaria setifolia</i> Fine-leaved Finger Grass	2	2
<i>Diheteropogon fillifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	1	1
<i>Helictotrichon turgidulum</i> Helictotrichon	**	**
<i>Koeleria capensis</i> Koeleria	1	1
<i>Stiburus alopecuroides</i> Stiburus	3	3
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	6	6
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	13	13
INCREASES II		
<i>Agrostis eriantha</i> Agrostis	**	**
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	4	4
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	3	3
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	21	23
<i>Sporobolus centrifugus</i> Olive Dropseed	**	**
<i>Paspalum notatum</i> Bahia Grass	**	1
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	9	9
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	1	1
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	38	31
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 1.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MIDSLOPE / WETLAND ECOTONE	
	SITE 2	
	2009	
	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 1.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 1.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MIDSLOPE / WETLAND ECOTONE	
	SITE 2	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	49	56
Increaser I species (%)	13	13
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	28	31
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough frequencies**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 1.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 2
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 1.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MIDSLOPE / WETLAND ECOTONE	
	SITE 2	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	16	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	31	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	MEDIUM	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	47	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.83	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	LOW	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	5171	
Fuel load potential (from Table 1.4)	VERY HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	797	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	75.2	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%)		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	668	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	WELL MANAGED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	1.7	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 2.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG GOEDGEVONDEN	CREST	
	Dolerite / Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 3a	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
2009		
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	2	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	3222	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 15.9"	
East	30° 28' 25.5"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1661	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	160°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	6	6
<i>Monocymbium ceresiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	2	2
<i>Setaria sphacelata</i> Common Bristle Grass / Gewone Mannagras	**	**
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	7	9
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	15	17
INCREASERS I		
<i>Helictotrichon turgidulum</i> Helictotrichon	**	**
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	**	**
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	1	1
<i>Sporobolus centrifugus</i> Olive Dropseed	**	**
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	1	1
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	6	6
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	1	1
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	4	4
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	46	51
<i>Microchloa caffra</i> Pinchushion Grass / Elsgras	4	4
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> Veld Paspalum	3	3
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	11	13
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	9	9
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	0	0
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	84	82
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 2.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 3a	
	2009	
SITE 3A HAS RED DATA SPECIES	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 2.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 2.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 3a	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	15	17
Increaser I species (%)	1	1
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	75	82
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 2.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 3a
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	X
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 2.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 3a	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	2	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	15	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	17	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	32	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.95	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	POOR	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	3222	
Fuel load potential (from Table 2.4)	HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	547	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	45.4	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	403	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.2	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 3.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG GOEDGEVONDEN	CREST	
	Dolerite - Glenrosa	
	SITE 3b	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	3260	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 16' 44.3"	
East	30° 28' 46.5"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1635	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	90°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Stab Grass / Tweevingergras	**	**
<i>Digitaria tricholaenoides</i> Purple Finger Grass	1	1
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	**	**
<i>Monocymbium ceresiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	2	2
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	21	24
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	24	27
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	**	1
<i>Ctenium concinnum</i> Sickie Grass / Sekelgras	**	**
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	**	**
<i>Loudetia simplex</i> Common Russet Grass / Stingelgras	**	**
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	3	4
<i>Sporobolus centrifugus</i> Olive Dropseed	**	**
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	2	2
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	5	7
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	6	7
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	3	3
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	4	4
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	41	49
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	3	3
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	14	14
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	0	0
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	71	66
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 3.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 3b	
	2009	
	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 3.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 3.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 3b	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	24	27
Increaser I species (%)	5	7
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	57	66
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 3.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 3b
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	X
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 3.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 3b	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	17	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	28	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	43	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.24	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	3260	
Fuel load potential (from Table 3.4)	HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	640	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	55.4	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	492	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.0	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 4.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG GOEDGEVONDEN	MIDSLOPE	
	Dolerite - Mispah	
	SITE 5	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	2	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	2500	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 40.6"	
East	30° 28' 51.5"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1615	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	0°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	3	4
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	3	3
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	6	7
INCREASES I		
<i>Ctenium concinnum</i> Sickie Grass	2	2
<i>Rendlia altera</i> Mahem's Crest / Kleinrolblaar	7	9
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	1	1
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	12	12
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	22	24
INCREASES II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	7	7
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	3	4
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	38	42
<i>Microchloa caffra</i> Pinchusion Grass / Elsgras	7	12
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	4	4
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	4	4
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	9	9
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	72	69
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 4.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 5	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 4.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 4.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 5	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	6	7
Increaser I species (%)	22	24
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	59	69
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which decrease when veld is over-utilized or burned too frequently
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is under-utilized or not burned in high enough frequencies
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies

Table 4.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 5
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 4.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 5	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	2	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	11	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	31	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	MEDIUM	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	42	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.45	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	2500	
Fuel load potential (from Table 4.4)	MEDIUM	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	561	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	38.6	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	343	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	LOW	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.3	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 5.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Lunenburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG GOEDGEVONDEN	CREST	
	Dolerite / Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 6	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	4500	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 18' 06.1"	
East	30° 29' 23.4"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1648	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	280°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Stab Grass / Tweevingergras	**	**
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	**	1
<i>Monocymbium cerasiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	**	**
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	6	6
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	6	7
INCREASES I		
<i>Diheteropogon filifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	1	1
<i>Rendlia altera</i> Mahem's Crest / Kleinrolblaar	6	6
<i>Trachypogon spicatus</i> Giant Spear Grass / Reusepylgras	3	3
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	10	10
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	20	20
INCREASES II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	3	3
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	4	6
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	4	4
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	54	60
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	6	6
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	3	3
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	74	73
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 5.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 6	
	2009	
SITE 6 HAS RED DATA SPECIES	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 5.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 5.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 6	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	6	7
Increaser I species (%)	20	20
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	65	73
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 5.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 6
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 5.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 6	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	12	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	21	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	34	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.94	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	POOR	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	2500	
Fuel load potential (from Table 5.4)	MEDIUM	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	622	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	49.2	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	437	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.1	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

**GRASS SPECIES TABLES – FULL SURVEYS
LA BELLA ESPERANZA**

Table 6.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG LA BELLE ESPERANZA	CREST	
	Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 6	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	4	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	6159	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	3	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 16' 47.2"	
East	30° 34' 31.4"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1313	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	80°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Brachiaria serrata</i> Velvet Signal Grass / Fluweelsinjalgras	1	1
<i>Diheteropogon amplexans</i> Broad-leaved Bluestem / Breeblaar Andropogon	1	1
<i>Monocymbium ceresiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	**	**
<i>Panicum natalense</i> Natal Buffalo Grass / Natal Buffelsgras	**	**
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	**	1
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	2	3
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloterpis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	1	1
<i>Ctenium concinnum</i> Sickie Grass	**	**
<i>Cymbopogon excavatus</i> Common Turpentine Grass / Lemoengras	2	3
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	22	31
<i>Rendlia altera</i> Mahem's Crest / Kleinrolblaar	6	7
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	15	19
<i>Trachypogon spicatus</i> Giant Spear Grass / Reusepylgras	1	1
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	20	22
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	67	84
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	**	1
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	1	3
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> Veld Paspalum	4	6
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	2	3
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	19	19
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	5	5
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	31	13
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 6.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 6	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 6.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 6.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 6	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	2	3
Increaser I species (%)	67	84
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	7	13
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100
Veld Condition (Tainton's Method)	OVER-RESTED/CLIMAX	

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 6.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 6
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 6.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 6	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	4	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	17	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	27	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	44	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.43	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (3 tons per ha = threshold for burning climax veld)	1313	
Fuel load potential (from Table 6.4)	LOW	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	622	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	49.2	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	437	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	SELECTIVELY GRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.1	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 7.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG LA BELLE ESPERANZA	CREST	
	Dolerite - Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 7	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	4	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	3325	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 48.7"	
East	30° 32' 14.8"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1611	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	120°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon chinensis</i> Hairy Bluegrass / Tweevingergras	1	1
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Gesteektegras	1	1
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	4	4
<i>Panicum ecklonii</i> Small Panicum	**	1
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	9	11
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	15	18
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	4	4
<i>Ctenium concinnum</i> Sickle Grass	**	**
<i>Diheteropogon filifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	1	1
<i>Eulalia villosa</i> Yellow Velvet Grass / Geelftuweelgras	**	**
<i>Harpochloa falx</i> Caterpillar Grass / Ruspergras	3	4
<i>Helictotrichon turgidulum</i> Helictotrichon	1	1
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	14	17
<i>Melinis nerviglumis</i> Bristle-leaved Red Top / Steekblaarblinkgras	**	**
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	2	2
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-driëblomgras	**	**
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	25	29
INCREASERS II		
<i>Aristida transvaalensis</i> Rock Three Awn	1	1
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	18	21
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	16	20
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	4	6
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	1	2
<i>Microchloa caffra</i> Pinchusion Grass / Elsgras	1	1
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taai-pol	**	1
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	17	17
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	1	1
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	59	52
Unidentified	1	1
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 7.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 7	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 7.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 7.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 7	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	15	18
Increaser I species (%)	25	29
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	41	52
Unidentified species (%)	1	1
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 7.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 7
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	X
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 7.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 7	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	4	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	23	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	HIGH	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	19	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	42	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.07	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (3 tons per ha = threshold for burning climax veld)	3325	
Fuel load potential (from Table 7.4)	HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	633	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	43.0	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	382	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	LOW	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	SELECTIVELY GRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.2	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 8.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG LA BELLE ESPERANZA	MIDSLOPE	
	Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 8	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	5	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	6861	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	4	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 07.8"	
East	30° 33' 07.8"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1384	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	120°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	1	3
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	1	3
INCREASERS I		
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	30	47
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	30	47
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	3	4
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	4	7
<i>Paspalum notatum</i> Bahia Grass	5	5
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> Veld Paspalum	7	13
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	17	21
<i>Sporobolus pyramidalis</i> Catstail Grass / Vleigras / Taaipol	**	**
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	30	30
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	3	3
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	69	50
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 8.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MIDSLLOPE	
	SITE 8	
	2009	
	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 8.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 8.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MIDSLLOPE	
	SITE 8	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	1	3
Increase I species (%)	30	47
Increase II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	36	50
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which decrease when veld is over-utilized or burned too frequently
Increase I species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is under-utilized or not burned in high enough
Increase II species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies

Table 8.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER:8
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 8.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MIDSLLOPE	
	SITE 8	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	5	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	MEDIUM	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	8	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	LOW	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	21	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	29	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.07	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (3 tons per ha = threshold for burning climax veld)	6861	
Fuel load potential (from Table 8.4)	VERY HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	589	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	35.0	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	311	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	LOW	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	SELECTIVELY GRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.4	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 9.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG LA BELLE ESPERANZA	MIDSLOPE	
	Dolerite - Mispah / Glenrosa	
	SITE 9	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	4384	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 38.4"	
East	30° 33' 04.4"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1428	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	30°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i> Vlei Bluestem / Vleiblougras	2	2
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Gesteektegras	3	3
<i>Diheteropogon amplexans</i> Broad-leaved Bluestem / Breeblaar Andropogon	10	10
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	1	1
<i>Monocymbium cerasiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	1	1
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	20	26
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	37	43
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	4	4
<i>Bewisia biflora</i> False Love Grass	3	3
<i>Ctenium concinnum</i> Sickie Grass / Sekelgras	2	2
<i>Diheteropogon filifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	7	7
<i>Eulalia villosa</i> Yellow Velvet Grass / Geelfluweelgras	**	**
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	3	4
<i>Melinis nerviglumis</i> Bristle-leaved Red Top / Steekblaarblinkgras	4	4
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	9	9
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	32	33
INCREASERS II		
<i>Aristida transvaalensis</i> Rock Three Awn	2	2
<i>Axonopus affinis</i> Axonopus	1	1
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	7	7
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	4	4
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	3	3
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> Veld Paspalum	4	4
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	3	3
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	7	7
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	0	0
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	31	24
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 9.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MID-SLOPE	
	SITE 9	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 9.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 9.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MID-SLOPE	
	SITE 9	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	37	43
Increaser I species (%)	32	33
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	24	24
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which decrease when veld is over-utilized or burned too frequently
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is under-utilized or not burned in high enough
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies

Table 9.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER:9
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 9.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MID-SLOPE	
	SITE 9	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	21	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	HIGH	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	18	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	39	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.21	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	4384	
Fuel load potential (from Table 9.4)	VERY HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	642	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	52.3	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	464	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	WELL MANAGED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.1	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

**GRASS SPECIES TABLES – FULL SURVEYS
PAARDEPLAATS**

Table 10.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG PAARDEPLAATS	CREST / MIDSLOPE	
	Dolerite - Glenrosa	
	SITE 1A	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	4	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	3472	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 15' 36.0"	
East	30° 28' 30.9"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1679	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	90°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Brachiaria serrata</i> Velvet Signal Grass / Fluweelsinjalgras	1	1
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	19	23
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	20	24
INCREASERS I		
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	19	21
<i>Melinis nerviglumis</i> Bristle-leaved Red Top / Steekblaarblinkgras	**	**
<i>Sporobolus centrifugus</i> Olive Dropseed	3	3
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	22	24
INCREASERS II		
<i>Aristida transvaalensis</i> Rock Three Awn	3	3
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	12	20
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	3	3
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	6	6
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	11	20
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	**	**
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	17	17
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	6	6
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	58	52
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 10.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST / MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 1A	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 10.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 10.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST / MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 1A	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	20	24
Increaser I species (%)	22	24
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	58	52
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 10.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 1A
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	X
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 10.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	ROCKY CREST	
	SITE 4	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	4	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	11	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	22	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	33	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.1	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	3472	
Fuel load potential (from Table 10.4)	HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	691	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	51.4	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	456	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	SELECTIVELY GRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.1	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 11.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG PAARDEPLAATS	CREST	
	Dolerite / Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 1B	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	3858	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 15' 06.1"	
East	30° 28' 07.2"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1693	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	40°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Stab Grass / Tweevingergras	3	3
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	4	6
<i>Monocymbium ceresiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	17	26
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	24	27
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	48	62
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	1	1
<i>Sporobolus centrifugus</i> Olive Dropseed	1	1
<i>Trachypogon spicatus</i> Giant Spear Grass / Reusepylgras	2	3
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	4	5
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	**	**
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	6	9
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	23	24
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	6	6
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	13	13
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	48	33
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 11.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 1B	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 11.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 11.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 1B	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	48	62
Increaser I species (%)	4	5
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	48	33
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 11.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 1B
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	X
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 11.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 1B	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	10	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	20	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	30	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.64	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	LOW	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	3858	
Fuel load potential (from Table 11.4)	HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	605	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	51.7	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	459	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.1	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 12.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG PAARDEPLAATS	CREST	
	Dolerite / Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 2	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	2939	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 15' 25.8"	
East	30° 28' 40.8"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1669	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	70°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	**	**
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	20	21
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	20	21
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	**	3
<i>Helictotrichon turgidulum</i> Helictotrichon	**	**
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	8	8
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	8	11
INCREASERS II		
<i>Aristida transvaalensis</i> Rock Three Awn	**	**
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	21	24
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	23	26
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	13	14
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	4	4
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	11	11
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	0	0
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	72	68
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 12.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 2	
	2009	
Geophyte or red data species recorded	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 12.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 12.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 2	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	20	21
Increaser I species (%)	8	11
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	72	68
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 12.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 2
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	X
less 2000	Low	

Table 12.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 2	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	10	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	18	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	28	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.17	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	2939	
Fuel load potential (from Table 12.4)	MEDIUM	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	703	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	54.8	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	487	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.0	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 13.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG PAARDEPLAATS	ROCKY CREST	
	Dolerite / Mispah & Glenrosa	
	SITE 4	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	2	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	1732	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 16' 40.1"	
East	30° 28' 42.1"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1628	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	15°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
No Decreaser species recorded		
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	0	0
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	**	2
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	24	30
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	2	3
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	26	35
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	13	19
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	2	4
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	3	4
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	17	24
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	12	14
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	6	7
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	2	3
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	56	65
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 13.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	ROCKY CREST	
	SITE 4	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 13.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 13.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	ROCKY CREST	
	SITE 4	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	21	0
Increase I species (%)	26	35
Increase II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	48	65
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increase I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increase II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 13.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 4
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	X

Table 13.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	ROCKY CREST	
	SITE 4	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	2	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	8	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	LOW	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	14	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	22	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.78	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	LOW	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	1732	
Fuel load potential (from Table 13.4)	LOW	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	661	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	46.8	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	416	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	SELECTIVELY GRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.1	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

**GRASS SPECIES TABLES – FULL SURVEYS
ZUURBRON**

Table 14.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG ZUURBRON	MIDSLOPE	
	Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 3A	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	2290	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 25.3"	
East	30° 27' 21.2"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1666	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	170°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon chinensis</i> Hairy Bluegrass / Tweevingergras	7	7
<i>Digitaria tricholaenoides</i> Purple Finger Grass	1	1
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	3	3
<i>Monocymbium ceresiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	3	3
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	4	4
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	18	18
INCREASERS I		
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	6	7
<i>Melinis nerviglumis</i> Bristle-leaved Red Top / Steekblaarblinkgras	**	**
<i>Setaria nigrirostris</i> Rootstock Manna Grass	4	4
<i>Trachypogon spicatus</i> Giant Spear Grass / Reusepylgras	9	9
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	6	6
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	25	26
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	1	1
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	1	1
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	43	51
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	3	3
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	9	9
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	0	0
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	57	56
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 14.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 3A	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 14.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 14.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 3A	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	18	18
Increaser I species (%)	25	26
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	48	56
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 14.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 3A
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	X
less 2000	Low	

Table 14.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 3A	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	14	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	32	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	MEDIUM	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	46	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.38	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	2290	
Fuel load potential (from Table 14.4)	MEDIUM	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	591	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	46.6	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	414	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.2	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 15.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG ZUURBRON	MIDSLOPE	
	Sandstone / Sandy	
	SITE 6	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	3787	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 18' 03.9"	
East	30° 25' 57.2"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1670	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	140°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Stab Grass / Tweevingergras	**	**
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	1	1
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	6	7
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	7	8
INCREASERS I		
<i>Diheteropogon filifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	2	2
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	4	4
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	3	3
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	9	9
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis chloromelas</i> Curly Leaf / Krulblaar	7	9
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	29	33
<i>Eragrostis gummiflua</i> Gum Grass	10	10
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	17	17
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	3	3
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	10	10
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaipol	1	1
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	3	3
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	4	4
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	84	83
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 15.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 6	
	2009	
	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 15.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 15.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 6	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	7	8
Increaser I species (%)	9	9
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	77	83
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 15.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 6
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	X
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 15.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 6	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	13	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	14	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	27	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.02	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	LOW	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	3787	
Fuel load potential (from Table 15.4)	HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	665	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	47.5	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	422	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.1	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 16.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG ZUURBRON	MIDSLOPE	
	Dolerite / Red Sand Clay Loam	
	SITE 7	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	2	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	4234	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 16' 43.7"	
East	30° 25' 41.6"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1735	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	100°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Digitaria tricholaenoides</i> Purple Finger Grass	1	1
<i>Monocymbium ceresiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	**	**
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	44	47
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	45	48
INCREASES I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	**	**
<i>Hyparrhenia dregeana</i> Thatching Grass	**	**
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	6	7
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	9	9
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	15	16
INCREASES II		
<i>Agrostis eriantha</i> Agrostis	**	**
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	3	3
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	16	17
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	1	3
<i>Paspalum dilatatum</i> Dallis Grass	**	**
<i>Sporobolus africanus</i> Ratstail Dropseed / Taaiopol	11	13
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	9	9
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	0	0
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	40	36
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 16.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 7	
	2009	
	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 16.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 16.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 7	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	45	48
Increaser I species (%)	15	16
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	31	36
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 16.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 7
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 16.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MIDSLOPE	
	SITE 7	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	2	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	13	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	27	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	40	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	2.46	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	MEDIUM	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	4234	
Fuel load potential (from Table 16.4)	VERY HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	796	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	70.4	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	625	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	WELL MANAGED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	1.8	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %)+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 17.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG ZUURBRON	MIDSLOPE	
	Dolerite / Mispah & Glenrosa	
	SITE 8	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	4016	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 44.3"	
East	30° 26' 38.4"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1673	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	120°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon chinensis</i> Hairy Bluegrass / Tweevingergras	6	6
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Stab Grass / Tweevingergras	**	**
<i>Brachiaria serrata</i> Velvet Signal Grass / Fluweelsinjalgras	1	1
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	3	4
<i>Monocymbium ceresiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	1	1
<i>Panicum ecklonii</i> Small Panicum	1	1
<i>Panicum natalense</i> Natal Buffalo Grass / Natal Buffelsgras	3	3
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	6	7
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	21	23
INCREASES I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	2	2
<i>Ctenium concinnum</i> Sickie Grass	1	1
<i>Diheteropogon filifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	1	1
<i>Eulalia villosa</i> Yellow Velvet Grass / Geelfluweelgras	1	1
<i>Harpochloa falx</i> Caterpillar Grass / Ruspergras	1	2
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	1	1
<i>Loudetia simplex</i> Common Russet Grass / Stingelgras	1	1
<i>Melinis nerviglumis</i> Bristle-leaved Red Top / Steekblaarblinkgras	4	5
<i>Rendlia altera</i> Mahem's Crest / Kleinrolblaar	5	7
<i>Trachypogon spicatus</i> Giant Spear Grass / Reusepylgras	23	24
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	2	3
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	42	48
INCREASES II		
<i>Aristida transvaalensis</i> Rock Three Awn	6	6
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	1	1
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	8	9
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	5	6
<i>Microchloa caffra</i> Pinchusion Grass / Elsgras	5	7
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	11	11
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	1	1
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	37	29
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 17.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	MID-SLOPE	
	SITE 8	
	2009	
	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 17.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 17.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	MID-SLOPE	
	SITE 8	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	21	23
Increaser I species (%)	42	48
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	25	29
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which decrease when veld is over-utilized or burned too frequently
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is under-utilized or not burned in high enough frequencies
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies

Table 17.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 8
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 17.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	MID-SLOPE	
	SITE 8	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	24	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	HIGH	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	18	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	42	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.55	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	LOW	
FUEL LOAD (3 tons per ha = threshold for burning climax veld)	4016	
Fuel load potential (from Table 17.4)	VERY HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	701	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	36.5	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	324	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	LOW	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVER-RESTED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.4	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

**GRASS SPECIES TABLES – FULL SURVEYS
BERGVLIET**

Table 18.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG BERGVLIET	CREST	
	Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 1	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	2876	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 50.3"	
East	30° 30' 08.4"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1634	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	120°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	4	4
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	18	20
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	22	24
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	4	4
<i>Diheteropogon filifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	1	1
<i>Rendlia altera</i> Mahem's Crest / Kleinrolblaar	5	5
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	10	10
INCREASERS II		
<i>Eragrostis curvula</i> Weeping Love Grass / Oulandsgras	7	9
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	**	**
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	2	2
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	48	55
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	9	9
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	2	2
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	68	66
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 18.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 1	
	2009	
	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 18.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 18.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 1	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	22	24
Increaser I species (%)	10	10
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	57	66
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which **decrease** when veld is **over-utilized or burned too frequently**
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **under-utilized or not burned in high enough**
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which **increase** when veld is **over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies**

Table 18.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 1
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	X
less 2000	Low	

Table 18.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 1	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	9	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	LOW	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	14	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	23	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.68	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	POOR	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	2876	
Fuel load potential (from Table 18.4)	MEDIUM	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	637	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	53.3	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	473	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.0	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 19.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG BERGVLIET	CREST /MIDLOPE	
	Dolerite - Mispah	
	SITE 2	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	2213	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	2	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 20.4"	
East	30° 30' 42.9"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1614	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	250°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Andropogon schirensis</i> Gesteektegras	**	**
<i>Eragrostis capensis</i> Heart-seed Love Grass / Hartjiesgras	3	3
<i>Panicum natalense</i> Natal Buffalo Grass / Natal Buffelsgras	**	**
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	1	1
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	4	4
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	1	1
<i>Ctenium concinnum</i> Sickie Grass	**	**
<i>Harpochloa falx</i> Caterpillar Grass / Ruspergras	1	1
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	1	1
<i>Loudetia simplex</i> Common Russet Grass / Stingelgras	**	**
<i>Melinis nerviglumis</i> Bristle-leaved Red Top / Steekblaarblinkgras	6	9
<i>Rendlia altera</i> Mahem's Crest / Kleinrolblaar	9	9
<i>Sporobolus centrifugus</i> Olive Dropseed	**	**
<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i> Hairy Trident Grass / Harige-drieblomgras	**	**
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	18	21
INCREASERS II		
<i>Aristida transvaalensis</i> Rock Three Awn	27	33
<i>Digitaria monodactyla</i> One Finger Grass / Eenvingergras	**	3
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	**	**
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	7	9
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	23	24
<i>Microchloa caffra</i> Pinchusion Grass / Elsgras	5	6
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	6	6
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	10	10
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	78	75
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 19.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST /MID Slope	
	SITE 2	
	2009	
	See Plant Diversity Assessment	

Table 19.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 19.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST /MID Slope	
	SITE 2	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	4	4
Increaser I species (%)	18	21
Increaser II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	62	75
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which decrease when veld is over-utilized or burned too frequently
Increaser I species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is under-utilized or not burned in high enough
Increaser II species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies

Table 19.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER: 2
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	X
less 2000	Low	

Table 19.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST /MID Slope	
	SITE 2	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	19	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	23	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	42	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	MEDIUM	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.98	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	LOW	
FUEL LOAD (4 tons per ha = threshold for burning)	2213	
Fuel load potential (from Table 19.4)	MEDIUM	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	463	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	MODERATE	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	28.0	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	249	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY LOW	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	OVERGRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.6	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %))+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

Table 20.1: Veld condition assessment table*: Grass species cover and composition at Luneburg (2009) for the WWF/SANBI Grassland Biome Conservation Project.

LUNEBURG BERGVLIET	CREST	
	Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam	
	SITE 3	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCES (in cm) : <5cm = Good, 5-6cm = Moderate, >6cm = Poor	3	
PHYTOMASS / FUEL LOAD (in kg/ha)	5090	
ORGANIC ACCUMULATION / COVER: 1 = Low, 5 = High	1	
CO-ORDINATES: South	27° 17' 32.2"	
East	30° 30' 45.6"	
HEIGHT ABOVE SEA LEVEL (m)	1628	
DIRECTION OF TRANSECT	60°	
Mucina & Rutherford Vegetation - Mesic Highveld Grassland Bioregion	Vegetation Unit - GM 14 = Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland	
Acock's Veld Type - Grassland Biome	Veld Type 63 - Piet Retief Sourveld	
GRASS SPECIES IN CATEGORIES		
DECREASERS		
<i>Monocymbium cerasiiforme</i> Boat Grass / Bootjiesgras	3	3
<i>Themeda triandra</i> Rooigras	14	16
TOTAL (Decreaser category):	17	19
INCREASERS I		
<i>Alloteropsis semialata</i> Black-seed Grass / Donkersaadgras	1	1
<i>Diheteropogon filifolius</i> Thread-leaved Bluestem / Smalblaarblougras	1	1
<i>Hyparrhenia hirta</i> Common Thatching Grass	4	4
<i>Rendlia altera</i> Mahem's Crest / Kleinrolblaar	38	39
<i>Trachypogon spicatus</i> Giant Spear Grass / Reusepylgras	1	1
TOTAL (Increaser I cat.):	45	46
INCREASERS II		
<i>Aristida transvaalensis</i> Rock Three Awn	6	7
<i>Eragrostis plana</i> Tough Love Grass	10	10
<i>Eragrostis racemosa</i> Narrow Heart Love Grass / Smalhartjiesgras	3	3
<i>Heteropogon contortus</i> Spear Grass / Assegaaigras	15	15
Dicot Herbaceous Perennial Forbs	4	4
Monocot Forbs, including sedges (Cyperaceae)	0	0
Bare Ground	0	0
TOTAL (Increaser II cat.):	38	35
Unidentified	0	0
TOTAL	100	100

* Table format amendments by Prof W.S.W. Trollope - YELLOW HIGHLIGHTS KEY GRASS SPECIES.

** Less than 1% of species recorded at site

Table 20.2: Other non-grass herbaceous plant, including protected or geophyte species.

OTHER HERBACEOUS SPECIES	CREST	
	SITE 3	
	2009	
SITE 3 HAS RED DATA SPECIES	See plant species diversity assessment	

Table 20.3: Trends in species composition, from Table 20.1.

VELD CONDITION SUMMARY OF TREND (TAINTON'S METHOD)	CREST	
	SITE 3	
	Incl. Sedges & Forbs	Excl. Sedges & Forbs
	2009	
Decreaser species (%)	17	19
Increase I species (%)	45	46
Increase II species, excluding forbs and sedges (%)	34	35
Unidentified species (%)	0	0
Bare Ground (%)	0	0
Total (%)	100	100

Legend: *Decreaser species* - Grass and herbaceous species which decrease when veld is over-utilized or burned too frequently
Increase I species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is under-utilized or not burned in high enough
Increase II species - Grass and herbaceous species which increase when veld is over-utilized or burned in too high frequencies

Table 20.4 : Fuel load (in kg/ha).

VOLUME (kg/ha)	POTENTIAL	SITE NUMBER:3
		2009
> 4 000	Very High	X
3 000-4 000	High	
2 000-3 000	Medium	
less 2000	Low	

Table 20.5: Summary.

SUMMARY	CREST	
	SITE 3	
	2009	
TUFT DISTANCE (cm)	3	
Water Catchment Potential (High is 1-4 cm, Medium 5-6 cm & Low > 6 cm)	HIGH	
GRASS SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	12	
Grass Species Richness (High is = 20-30 spp, Low < 10 species)	MEDIUM	
FORB SPECIES RICHNESS (per 2500 square meters)	17	
Forb Species Richness (High is = >40 spp, Low < 30 species)	LOW	
TOTAL SPECIES RICHNESS (grasses and forbs)	29	
Total Species Richness (High is = >60 spp, Low < 40 species)	LOW	
FLORA DIVERSITY (Shannon Mean, Max = 4.5)	1.84	
Plant Diversity (High is >3.00, Low is < 2.0)	LOW	
FUEL LOAD (3 tons per ha = threshold for burning climax veld)	5090	
Fuel load potential (from Table 20.4)	VERY HIGH	
FUEL SCORE (From Key Species Table)	623	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY HIGH	
VELD CONDITION SCORE	30.4	
= Forage Score / 888 x 100%		
FORAGE SCORE (From Key Species Table)	270	
>600 Very high; 501-600 High; 401-500 Moderate; 301-400 Low; <301 Very low	VERY LOW	
VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT	SELECTIVELY GRAZED	
GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LSU)	2.5	
= 365 / (-31.159+(1.433xVCS %)+Rainfall-419.7)x0.231		

**KEY GRASS SPECIES
GOEDGEVONDEN**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 24:

SAMPLE SITE: Goedgevonden - Site 5

GPS: S - S 27° 17' 40.6"

DATE: 11/02/2009

E - E 30° 28' 51.5"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Mispah

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	3	6	18	5	15
DECREASER TOTAL		3	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	0	3	0	5	0
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	7	-4	-28	1	7
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	12	3	36	5	60
INCREASER I TOTAL		19	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	38	2	76	1	38
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	7	2	14	4	28
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	7	-6	-42	-7	-49
FORBS		13	-3	-39	-2	-26
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		65	*****		*****	
OTHERS		13	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	343	TOTAL	561
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			38.6			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING		
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High			HPG? xxx	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High		xxx	HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium			REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low	xxx		Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward.	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO	7) TREND		
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6	CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION
2.3 ha/AU			Current* = 1 AU: 2.4	Decreaser	3	Correctly stocked
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				Increase I	19	Selectively Grazed
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;				Increase I	19	Under Stocked
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;				Increase II	65	Over Stocked
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.						xxx
3) STOCKING RATE*				COMMENT:		
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.				The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.		
				* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.		

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 4cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 2500		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	3		
INCREASER I	19		
INCREASER II	65		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 2500			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009
 Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 25:

SAMPLE SITE: Goedgevonden - Site 6

GPS: S - 27° 18' 06.1"

DATE: 24/02/2009

E - 30° 29' 23.4"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	6	6	36	5	30
DECREASER TOTAL		6	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	0	3	0	5	0
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	6	-4	-24	1	6
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	10	3	30	5	50
INCREASER I TOTAL		16	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	54	2	108	1	54
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	3	2	6	4	12
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
FORBS		9	-3	-27	-2	-18
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		66	*****		*****	
OTHERS		12	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	437	TOTAL	622
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			49.2			

CONCLUSIONS																									
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING																					
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx																				
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG? xxx	Vigour?																				
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?																				
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:																				
301 - 400	Low			Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward.	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.																				
<301	Very Low																								
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO*																						
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall – 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6																						
2.1 ha/AU			Current* = 1 AU: 2.4																						
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.																						
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;																									
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;																									
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall – mm.																									
3) STOCKING RATE*			7) TREND																						
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.			<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>CATEGORY</th> <th>%</th> <th>UTILIZATION</th> <th>tick</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Decreaser</td> <td>6</td> <td>Correctly stocked</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Increase I</td> <td>16</td> <td>Selectively Grazed</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Increase I</td> <td>16</td> <td>Under Stocked</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Increase II</td> <td>66</td> <td>Over Stocked</td> <td>xxx</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION	tick	Decreaser	6	Correctly stocked		Increase I	16	Selectively Grazed		Increase I	16	Under Stocked		Increase II	66	Over Stocked	xxx
CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION	tick																						
Decreaser	6	Correctly stocked																							
Increase I	16	Selectively Grazed																							
Increase I	16	Under Stocked																							
Increase II	66	Over Stocked	xxx																						
			COMMENT: The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.																						

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤ 4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance – cm = 4cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 4500		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			xxx

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	6		
INCREASER I	16		
INCREASER II	66		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 4500		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

**KEY GRASS SPECIES
LA BELLA ESPERANZA**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 26:

SAMPLE SITE: La Bella Esperanza - Site 6

GPS: S - 27° 16' 47.2"

DATE: 12/02/2009

E - 30° 34' 31.4"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	0	6	0	5	0
DECREASER TOTAL		0	*****	*****	*****	*****
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	22	3	66	5	110
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	6	-4	-24	1	6
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	20	3	60	5	100
INCREASER I TOTAL		48	*****	*****	*****	*****
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	0	2	0	1	0
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	0	2	0	4	0
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	FORBS	24	-3	-72	-2	-48
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		24	*****	*****	*****	*****
OTHERS		28	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	338	TOTAL	656
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			38.1			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL		5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG? xxx	Seeding? Xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG?	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium			REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low	xxx		The high proportions of Increase I and II grass species indicate selective grazing necessitating burning and High Utilization Grazing	Rotational resting to maximise the seeding of Decreaser grass species like <i>Themeda triandra</i> is a top priority to increase the forage score and resultant grazing capacity of the grass sward	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO *		7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = LAU: 6		CATEGORY % UTILIZATION tick	
2.3 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 2.5		Decreaser 0 Correctly stocked	
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT:		Increase I 48 Selectively Grazed xxx	
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.		Increase I 48 Under Stocked	
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II 24 Over Stocked	
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					COMMENT:	
3) STOCKING RATE*					The significant proportions of Increase I and II grass species is a clear indication that the grass sward has been subjected to selective grazing necessitating reassessing the livestock ratio of cattle to sheep. This would probably require a decrease in the stocking rate of sheep and an increase in the numbers of cattle.	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.						

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤ 4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 4cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 6159		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			xxx

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	0		
INCREASER I	48	xxx	
INCREASER II	24		
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 6159		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 27:

SAMPLE SITE: La Bella Esperanza - Site 7

GPS: S - 27° 17' 48.7"

DATE: 12/02/2009

E - 30° 32' 14.8"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	9	6	54	5	45
DECREASER TOTAL		9	*****	*****	*****	*****
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia species</i>	14	3	42	5	70
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		14	*****	*****	*****	*****
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	1	2	2	1	1
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	18	2	36	4	72
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	1	-6	-6	-7	-7
	FORBS	18	-3	-54	-2	-36
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		38	*****	*****	*****	*****
OTHERS		39	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	382	TOTAL	633
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			43.0			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING		5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG? xxx	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG?	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium			REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low	xxx		The high proportions of Increase I and II grass species indicate selective grazing necessitating burning and High Utilization Grazing	Rotational resting to maximise the seeding of Decreaser grass species like <i>Themeda triandra</i> is a top priority to increase the forage score and resultant grazing capacity of the grass sward	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO *		7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6		CATEGORY % UTILIZATION tick	
2.2 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 2.5		Decreaser 9 Correctly stocked	
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT:		Increase I 14 Selectively Grazed xxx	
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.		Increase I 14 Under Stocked	
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II 38 Over Stocked	
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					COMMENT:	
3) STOCKING RATE					The significant proportions of Increase I and II grass species is a clear indication that the grass sward has been subjected to selective grazing necessitating reassessing the livestock ratio of cattle to sheep. This would probably require a decrease in the stocking rate of sheep and an increase in the numbers of cattle.	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.						

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤ 4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 4cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 3325			xxx
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			xxx

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	9		
INCREASER I	14		
INCREASER II	38		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 3325			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 28:

SAMPLE SITE: La Bella Esperanza - Site 8

GPS: S - 27° 17' 07.8"

DATE: 12/02/2009

E - 30° 33' 07.8"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	1	6	6	5	5
DECREASER TOTAL		1	*****	*****	*****	*****
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	30	3	90	5	150
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		30	*****	*****	*****	*****
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	0	2	0	1	0
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	3	2	6	4	12
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	FORBS	33	-3	-99	-2	-66
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		36	*****	*****	*****	*****
OTHERS		33	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	CONSTANT	311	TOTAL	589
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			35.0			

CONCLUSIONS																									
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING																					
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG? xxx	Seeding? xxx																				
>600	Very High			HPG?	Vigour?																				
501 - 600	High		xxx	HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?																				
401 - 500	Medium			REASON:	REASON:																				
301 - 400	Low	xxx		Increase I and II grass species indicate selective grazing necessitating burning and High Utilization	Rotational resting to maximise the seeding of Decreaser grass species like <i>Themeda triandra</i> is a top priority to increase the forage score and resultant grazing capacity of the grass sward																				
<301	Very Low																								
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO *																						
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall – 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6																						
2.4 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 2.5																						
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT:																						
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.																						
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;																									
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall – mm.																									
3) STOCKING RATE*			7) TREND																						
			<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>CATEGORY</th> <th>%</th> <th>UTILIZATION</th> <th>tick</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>Decreaser</td> <td>1</td> <td>Correctly stocked</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Increase I</td> <td>30</td> <td>Selectively Grazed</td> <td>xxx</td> </tr> <tr> <td>Increase I</td> <td>30</td> <td>Under Stocked</td> <td></td> </tr> <tr> <td>Increase II</td> <td>36</td> <td>Over Stocked</td> <td></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>			CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION	tick	Decreaser	1	Correctly stocked		Increase I	30	Selectively Grazed	xxx	Increase I	30	Under Stocked		Increase II	36	Over Stocked	
CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION	tick																						
Decreaser	1	Correctly stocked																							
Increase I	30	Selectively Grazed	xxx																						
Increase I	30	Under Stocked																							
Increase II	36	Over Stocked																							
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.			COMMENT:																						
			The significant proportions of Increase I and II grass species is a clear indication that the grass sward has been subjected to selective grazing necessitating reassessing the livestock ratio of cattle to sheep. This would probably require a decrease in the stocking rate of sheep and an increase in the numbers of cattle.																						

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤ 4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance – cm = 4cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH	LOW	
	<1500kg/ha	>1500kg/ha	
kg/ha = 6861		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	1		
INCREASER I	30	xxx	
INCREASER II	36		
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 6861		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

Comment: While the ecological condition of the grass sward is not ideal to withstand burning it is very moribund and of poor quality for grazing animals. Consequently it is recommended that veld in this condition on the farm be considered for burning provided that HPG grazing and a seeding rest are applied to encourage Decreaser grass species.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 29:

SAMPLE SITE: La Bella Esperanza - Site 9

GPS: S - 27° 17' 38.4"

DATE: 12/02/2009

E - 30° 33' 04.4"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Mispah & Glenrosa

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	2	14	28	11	22
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	20	6	120	5	100
DECREASER TOTAL		22	*****	*****	*****	*****
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia species</i>	3	3	9	5	15
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		3	*****	*****	*****	*****
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	3	2	6	1	3
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	7	2	14	4	28
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	FORBS	7	-3	-21	-2	-14
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		17	*****	*****	*****	*****
OTHERS		58	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	CONSTANT	464	TOTAL	642
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			52.3			

CONCLUSIONS								
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL		5) ROTATIONAL RESTING			
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx			
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG?	Vigour?			
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG? xxx	Fodder Reserve?			
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:			
301 - 400	Low							
<301	Very Low			The grass sward is in medium condition and the rotational grazing must comprise both High Utilization and High Production Grazing to maintain the dominance of Decreaser grass species.	Because there is a dominance of Decreaser grass species there is no necessity for a seeding rest but rather resting to maintain the vigour of the grass sward and provide for a fodder reserve for periods of scarcity			
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO *		7) TREND			
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6		CATEGORRY			
2.1 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 2.5		%	UTILIZATION tick		
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT:		Decreaser	22	Correctly stocked	xxx
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.		Increase I	3	Selectively Grazed	
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase I	3	Under Stocked	
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					Increase II	17	Over Stocked	
3) STOCKING RATE*					COMMENT:			
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.					Because there is a dominance of Decreaser grass species there is no necessity for a seeding rest but rather resting to maintain the vigour of the grass sward and provide for a fodder reserve for periods of scarcity			

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤ 4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 3cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 4384		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			xxx

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	22	xxx	
INCREASER I	3		
INCREASER II	17		
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 4384		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

**KEY GRASS SPECIES
PAARDEPLAATS**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 30:

SAMPLE SITE: Paardeplaats - Site 1a

GPS: S - 27° 15' 36.0"
E - 30° 28' 30.9"

DATE: 18-Feb-09

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite - Glenrosa

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatis</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	19	6	114	5	95
DECREASER TOTAL		19	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	19	3	57	5	95
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		19	*****		*****	
FORBS	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	11	2	22	1	11
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	12	2	24	4	48
	<i>Microchloa cafra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		46	*****		*****	
OTHERS		16	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	456	TOTAL	691
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			51.4			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL		5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG? xxx	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG?	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low			Increase I and II grass species indicate selective grazing necessitating burning and High Utilization	Rotational resting to maximise the seeding of Decreaser grass species like <i>Themeda triandra</i> is a top priority to increase the forage score and resultant grazing capacity of the grass sward	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO*		7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6		CATEGORY	%
2.1 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 4.3		Decreaser	19
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT:		Increase I	19
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.		Increase I	19
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II	46
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.						
3) STOCKING RATE*					COMMENT:	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.					The significant proportions of Increase I and II grass species is a clear indication that the grass sward has been subjected to selective grazing necessitating reassessing the livestock ratio of cattle to sheep. This would probably require a decrease in the stocking rate of sheep and an increase in the numbers of cattle.	

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 4cm			
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 3472			
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	19		
INCREASER I	19		
INCREASER II	46		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 3472			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

Comment: While the ecological condition of the grass sward is not ideal to withstand burning it is very moribund and of poor quality for grazing animals.

Consequently it is recommended that veld in this condition on the farm be considered for burning provided that HPG grazing and a seeding rest are applied to encourage Decreaser grass species.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 31:

SAMPLE SITE: Paardeplaats - Site 1b

GPS: S - 27° 15' 06.1"
E - 30° 28' 07.2"

DATE: 18-Feb-09

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	24	6	144	5	120
DECREASER TOTAL		24	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	0	3	0	5	0
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		0	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	23	2	46	1	23
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	0	2	0	4	0
	<i>Microchloa cafr</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
FORBS		13	-3	-39	-2	-26
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		36	*****		*****	
OTHERS		40	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	459	TOTAL	605
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			51.7			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION				4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG? xxx	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low			Apply High Production Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward.	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)				6) LIVESTOCK RATIO*	7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7) x 0.231)				Recommended = 1 AU: 6	CATEGORY	%
2.1 ha/AU				Current = 1 AU: 4.3	Decreaser	24
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				COMMENT: * Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.	Increase I	0
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;					Increase I	0
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II	36
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					Utilization	Correctly stocked
3) STOCKING RATE*					Under Stocked	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.					Over Stocked	xxx
					COMMENT: The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.	

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 3cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 3858		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	24		
INCREASER I	0		
INCREASER II	36		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 3858			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope - Associates: Working On Fire International - 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 32:

SAMPLE SITE: Paardeplaats - Site 2

GPS: S - 27° 15' 25.8"
E - 30° 28' 40.8"

DATE: 18-Feb-09

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	20	6	120	5	100
DECREASER TOTAL		20	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	8	3	24	5	40
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		8	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	13	2	26	1	13
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	21	2	42	4	84
	<i>Microchloa cafra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
FORBS		11	-3	-33	-2	-22
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		45	*****		*****	
OTHERS		27	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	487	TOTAL	703
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			54.8			

CONCLUSIONS							
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL		5) ROTATIONAL RESTING		
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx		
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG? xxx	Vigour?		
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?		
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:		
301 - 400	Low			Apply High Production Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.		
<301	Very Low						
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO*		7) TREND		
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6		CATEGORY		
2.0 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 4.3		UTILIZATION		
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT: * Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.		tick		
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;					Decreaser	20	Correctly stocked
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase I	8	Selectively Grazed
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.			Increase I	8	Under Stocked		
			Increase II	45	Over Stocked		
			COMMENT: The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.				
3) STOCKING RATE*							
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.							

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 3cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 1669		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	20		
INCREASER I	8		
INCREASER II	45		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 1669			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 33:

SAMPLE SITE: Paardeplaats - Site 4

GPS: S - 27° 16' 40.1"
E - 30° 28' 42.1"

DATE: 18-Feb-09

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite - Mispah & Glenrosa

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	0	6	0	5	0
DECREASER TOTAL		0	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	24	3	72	5	120
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		24	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	17	2	34	1	17
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	13	2	26	4	52
	<i>Microchloa cafra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
FORBS		8	-3	-24	-2	-16
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		38	*****		*****	
OTHERS		38	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	416	TOTAL	661
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			46.8			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION				4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG? xxx	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG?	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low			The high proportions of Increase I and II grass species indicate selective grazing necessitating burning and High Utilization Grazing	Rotational resting to maximise the seeding of Decreaser grass species like <i>Themeda triandra</i> is a top priority to increase the forage score and resultant grazing capacity of the grass sward	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)				6) LIVESTOCK RATIO*	7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)				Recommended = 1AU: 6	CATEGORY	%
2.1 ha/AU				Current = 1 AU: 4.3	Decreaser	0
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				COMMENT:	Increase I	24
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;				* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.	Increase I	24
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II	38
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					UTILIZATION	tick
3) STOCKING RATE*					Correctly stocked	
* Stocking Rate (& Livestock ratios) is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.					Selectively Grazed	xxx
					Under Stocked	
					Over Stocked	
					COMMENT:	
					The significant proportions of Increase I and II grass species is a clear indication that the grass sward has been subjected to selective grazing necessitating reassessing the livestock ratio of cattle to sheep. This would probably require a decrease in the stocking rate of sheep and an increase in the numbers of cattle.	

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 2cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 1732		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	0		
INCREASER I	24		
INCREASER II	38		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 1732			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

**KEY GRASS SPECIES
ZUURBRON**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 34:

SAMPLE SITE: Zuurbron - Site 3a

GPS: S - 27° 17' 25.3"

DATE: 24-Feb-09

E - 30° 27' 21.2"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	4	6	24	5	20
DECREASER TOTAL		4	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	6	3	18	5	30
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	6	-4	-24	1	6
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		12	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	43	2	86	1	43
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	1	2	2	4	4
	<i>Microchloa cafr</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	FORBS	0	-3	0	-2	0
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		44	*****		*****	
OTHERS		40	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	414	TOTAL	591
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			46.6			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION				4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG? xxx	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low			Apply High Production Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)				6) LIVESTOCK RATIO	7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)				Recommended = 1AU: 6	CATEGORY	%
2.2 ha/AU				Current = 1 AU: 6.9	Decreaser	4
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				COMMENT:	Increase I	12
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;				* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.	Increase I	12
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II	44
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					Over Stocked	xxx
3) STOCKING RATE*					COMMENT:	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.					The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.	

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 3cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 2290			xxx
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL	xxx		

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	4		
INCREASER I	12		
INCREASER II	44		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 2290			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;
 INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;
 INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.
 REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope - Associates: Working On Fire International - 3rd April, 2009
 Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 35:

SAMPLE SITE: Zuurbron - Site 6

GPS: S - 27° 18' 03.9"
E - 30° 25' 57.2"

DATE: 24-Feb-09

SOIL TYPE: Sandstone - Sandy

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatis</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	6	6	36	5	30
DECREASER TOTAL		6	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	4	3	12	5	20
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	3	3	9	5	15
INCREASER I TOTAL		7	*****		*****	
FORBS	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	10	2	20	1	10
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	29	2	58	4	116
	<i>Microchloa cafr</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		46	*****		*****	
OTHERS		41	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	422	TOTAL	665
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =				47.5		

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING		5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG? xxx	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low			Apply High Production Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.	
<301	Very Low					
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO		7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7) x 0.231)			Recommended = 1AU: 6		CATEGORY	%
2.1 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 6.9		Decreaser	6
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT:		Correctly Stocked	tick
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.		Increase I	7
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase I	7
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					Increase II	46
					Over Stocked	xxx
					COMMENT:	
					The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.	
3) STOCKING RATE*						
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.						

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 3cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 3787		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	6		
INCREASER I	7		
INCREASER II	46		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 3787			xxx
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			xxx

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;
 INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;
 INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope - Associates: Working On Fire International - 3rd April, 2009
 Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 36:

SAMPLE SITE: Zuurbron - Site 7

GPS: S - 27° 16' 43.7"
E - 30° 25' 41.6"

DATE: 24-Feb-09

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite - Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	44	6	264	5	220
DECREASER TOTAL		44	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	6	3	18	5	30
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	0	-4	0	1	0
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	9	3	27	5	45
INCREASER I TOTAL		15	*****		*****	
INCREASER II	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	1	2	2	1	1
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	3	2	6	4	12
	<i>Microchloa cafra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	FORBS	0	-3	0	-2	0
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		4	*****		*****	
OTHERS		37	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	625	TOTAL	796
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			70.4			

CONCLUSIONS							
1) VELD CONDITION				4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING		
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding?		
>600	Very High	xxx	xxx	HPG?	Vigour? xxx		
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG? xxx	Fodder Reserve? xxx		
401 - 500	Medium			REASON:	REASON:		
301 - 400	Low			The grass sward is in excellent condition and the rotational grazing must comprise both High Utilization and High Production Grazing to maintain the dominance of Decreaser grass species.	Because there is a dominance of Decreaser grass species there is no necessity for a seeding rest but rather resting to maintain the vigour of the grass sward and provide for a fodder reserve for periods of scarcity		
<301	Very Low						
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)				6) LIVESTOCK RATIO	7) TREND		
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7) x 0.231)				Recommended = 1 AU: 6	CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION
1.8 ha/AU				Current = 1 AU: 6.9	Decreaser	44	Correctly stocked
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				COMMENT: * Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.	Increase I	15	Selectively Grazed
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;					Increase I	15	Under Stocked
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II	4	Over Stocked
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					COMMENT: The dominance of Decreaser grass species indicates that the veld has been correctly stocked at the grazing capacity of the grass sward.		
3) STOCKING RATE*							
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.							

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤ 4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 2cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha		>1500kg/ha
kg/ha = 4234		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	44	xxx	
INCREASER I	15		
INCREASER II	4		
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 4234		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;
 INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;
 INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.
 REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009
 Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 37:

SAMPLE SITE: Zuurbron - Site 8

GPS: S - 27° 17' 44.3"
E - 30° 26' 38.4"

DATE: 24-Feb-09

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite - Mispah & Glenrosa

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatis</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	6	6	36	5	30
DECREASER TOTAL		6	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	0	3	0	5	0
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	23	-4	-92	1	23
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	42	3	126	5	210
INCREASER I TOTAL		65	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	5	2	10	1	5
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	1	2	2	4	4
	<i>Microchloa cafra</i>	5	-6	-30	-7	-35
FORBS		12	-3	-36	-2	-24
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		23	*****		*****	
OTHERS		6	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	324	TOTAL	701
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			36.5			

CONCLUSIONS						
1) VELD CONDITION				4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG? xxx	Seeding? xxx	
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG?	Vigour?	
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?	
401 - 500	Medium			REASON:	REASON:	
301 - 400	Low	xxx		Apply High Utilization Grazing to reduce the Increase I grass species which are less adapted to intensive grazing compared to Decreaser grass species.	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.	
<301	Very Low			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO	7) TREND	
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)				Recommended = 1 AU: 6	CATEGORY	%
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7)x 0.231)				Current = 1 AU: 6.9	Decreaser	6
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				COMMENT:	Increase I	65
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;				* Livestock Ratio is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.	Increase I	65
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increase II	23
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					COMMENT:	
3) STOCKING RATE*					The overall dominance of Increase I grass species indicates that the grass sward has been undergrazed probably due to understocking of veld in this condition. While the grazing capacity of the grass sward is lower it requires intensive High Utilization Grazing to reduce the dominance of Increase I grass species that are less adapted to intensive grazing. However, this must be combined with a program of regular rotational resting to promote an increase in Decreaser grass species through seeding.	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.						

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 3cm			
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH	LOW	
	<1500kg/ha	>1500kg/ha	
kg/ha = 4016		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	6		
INCREASER I	65	xxx	
INCREASER II	23		
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 4016		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;
 INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;
 INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.
 REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope - Associates: Working On Fire International - 3rd April, 2009
 Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

**KEY GRASS SPECIES
BERGVLIET**

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 38:

SAMPLE SITE: Bergvliet - Site 1

GPS: S - 27° 17' 50.3"

DATE: 23/02/2009

E - 30° 30' 08.4"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	18	6	108	5	90
DECREASER TOTAL		18	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia species</i>	0	3	0	5	0
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	5	-4	-20	1	5
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		5	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	48	2	96	1	48
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	7	2	14	4	28
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	FORBS	11	-3	-33	-2	-22
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		66	*****		*****	
OTHERS		11	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	473	TOTAL	637
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =				53.3		

CONCLUSIONS					
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx
>600	Very High		xxx	HPG? xxx	Vigour?
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?
401 - 500	Medium	xxx		REASON:	REASON:
301 - 400	Low			Apply High Production Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward.	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the grass sward.
<301	Very Low				
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO*	7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall - 419.7) x 0.231)			Recommended = 1 AU: 6	CATEGORY	%
2.0 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 4.1	Decreaser	18
Where: (Danczkewits 1981)			COMMENT:	Increase I	5
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			* Livestock ratio is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.	Increase I	5
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;				Increase II	66
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall - mm.					
3) STOCKING RATE*				COMMENT:	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.				The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.	

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance - cm = 4cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH	LOW	
	>1500kg/ha	<1500kg/ha	
kg/ha = 6861		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	18		
INCREASER I	5		
INCREASER II	66		xxx
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 6861		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;
 INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;
 INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.
 REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009
 Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

Comment: While the ecological condition of the grass sward is not ideal to withstand burning it is very moribund and of poor quality for grazing animals. Consequently it is recommended that veld in this condition on the farm be considered for burning provided that HPG grazing is applied to encourage Decreaser grass species.

Comment: While this estimated Mean Grazing Capacity is a realistic estimate of the grazing potential of veld in this condition it cannot be related to the grazing capacity of the farm as a whole. The Mean Grazing Capacity of the farm as a whole is discussed - the overall condition of the farm is calculated using the mean of the Veld Condition Scores for all the different sample sites.

COMMENT: The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 39:

SAMPLE SITE: Bergvliet - Site 2

GPS: S - 27° 17' 20.4"

DATE: 23/02/2009

E - 30° 30' 42.9"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Mispah & Glenrosa

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	1	6	6	5	5
DECREASER TOTAL		1	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	1	3	3	5	5
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	9	-4	-36	1	9
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		10	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	23	2	46	1	23
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	0	2	0	4	0
	<i>Microchloa caffra</i>	5	-6	-30	-7	-35
	FORBS	16	-3	-48	-2	-32
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		44	*****		*****	
OTHERS		45	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	249	TOTAL	463
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			28.0			

CONCLUSIONS					
1) VELD CONDITION			4) ROTATIONAL	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING	
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG?	Seeding? xxx
>600	Very High			HPG? xxx	Vigour?
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?
401 - 500	Medium		xxx	REASON:	REASON:
301 - 400	Low			Apply High Production Grazing to favour and promote Decreaser grass species in the grass sward.	Apply seeding rests as a priority to increase the proportion of Decreaser grass species in the grass sward thereby increasing the grazing capacity of the veld.
<301	Very Low	xxx			
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)			6) LIVESTOCK RATIO	7) TREND	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall – 419.7)x 0.231)			Recommended = 1 AU: 6	CATEGORY	%
2.6 ha/AU			Current = 1 AU: 4.1	Decreaser	1
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)			COMMENT:	Increase I	10
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;			Livestock ratio is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.	Increase I	10
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;				Increase II	44
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall – mm.					xxx
3) STOCKING RATE				COMMENT:	
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.				The dominance of Increase II grass species indicates that this sample site has been overstocked and its condition can be improved through the application of High Production Grazing and the application of rotational resting to promote Decreaser grass species.	

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤ 4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance – cm = 3cm	XXX		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH	LOW	
	>1500kg/ha	<1500kg/ha	
kg/ha = 2213		XXX	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		XXX	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	1		
INCREASER I	10		
INCREASER II	44		XXX
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 2213			XXX
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN			XXX

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)	
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall – 419.7)x 0.231)	
2.0 ha/AU	
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)	
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;	
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;	
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall – mm.	

Comment: While this estimated Mean Grazing Capacity is a realistic estimate of the grazing potential of veld in this condition it cannot be related to the grazing capacity of the farm as a whole. The Mean Grazing Capacity of the farm as a whole needs to be discussed in a separate section where the overall condition of the farm is calculated using the mean of the Veld Condition Scores for all the different sample sites

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

VELD CONDITION ASSESSMENT – KEY GRASS SPECIES
Wakkerstroom Montane Grassland - MPUMALANGA PROVINCE

TABLE 40:

SAMPLE SITE: Bergvliet - Site 3

GPS: S - 27° 17' 32.2" **DATE:** 23/02/2009

E - 30° 30' 45.6"

SOIL TYPE: Dolerite – Red Sandy Clay Loam

RECORDER: S.F. de Wet

CATEGORY	SPECIES	FREQUENCY %	FORAGE FACTOR	FORAGE SCORE	FUEL FACTOR	FUEL SCORE
DECREASER	<i>Andropogon appendiculatus</i>	0	14	0	11	0
	<i>Themeda triandra</i>	14	6	84	5	70
DECREASER TOTAL		14	*****		*****	
INCREASER I	<i>Hyparrhenia</i> species	4	3	12	5	20
SPECIES	<i>Rendlia altera</i>	38	-4	-152	1	38
	<i>Tristachya leucothrix</i>	0	3	0	5	0
INCREASER I TOTAL		42	*****		*****	
	<i>Heteropogon contortus</i>	15	2	30	1	15
	<i>Eragrostis curvula</i>	0	2	0	4	0
	<i>Microchloa cafra</i>	0	-6	0	-7	0
	FORBS	4	-3	-12	-2	-8
	BARE GROUND	0	-6	0	-7	0
INCREASER II TOTAL		19	*****		*****	
OTHERS		25	CONSTANT	308	CONSTANT	488
TOTAL		100	TOTAL	270	TOTAL	623
VELD CONDITION SCORE = Forage Score/ 888x100% =			30.4			

CONCLUSIONS								
1) VELD CONDITION				4) ROTATIONAL GRAZING	5) ROTATIONAL RESTING			
FORAGE/ FUEL SCORE	POTENTIAL	FORAGE tick	FUEL tick	HUG? xxx	Seeding? XXX			
>600	Very High		623	HPG?	Vigour?			
501 - 600	High			HUG/HPG?	Fodder Reserve?			
401 - 500	Medium			REASON:	REASON:			
301 - 400	Low			The high proportions of Increaser I and II grass species indicate selective grazing necessitating burning and High Utilization Grazing	Rotational resting to maximise the seeding of Decreaser grass species like <i>Themeda triandra</i> is a top priority to increase the forage score and resultant grazing capacity of the grass sward			
<301	Very Low	xxx						
2) MEAN GRAZING CAPACITY (ha/LAU)				6) LIVESTOCK RATIO	7) TREND			
GC = 365/(-31.159 + (1.433 x VCS%)) + ((Rainfall – 419.7)x 0.231)				Recommended = 1 AU: 6	CATEGORY	%	UTILIZATION	tick
2.5 ha/AU				Current = 1 AU: 4.1	Decreaser	14	Correctly stocked	
Where: (Danckwerts 1981)				COMMENT:	Increaser I	42	Selectively Grazed	xxx
GRAZING CAPACITY = Hectares/Animal Unit;				* Livestock ratio is applicable for the whole farm & not calculated per individual site.	Increaser I	42	Under Stocked	
VCS = Veld Condition Score expressed as %;					Increaser II	19	Over Stocked	
Rainfall = Previous 12 months rainfall – mm.					COMMENT: The significant proportions of Increaser I and II grass species is a clear indication that the grass sward has been subjected to selective grazing necessitating reassessing the livestock ratio of cattle to sheep. This would probably require a decrease in the stocking rate of sheep and an increase in the numbers of cattle.			
3) STOCKING RATE								
* Stocking Rate is applicable for the whole farm and not calculated for each per individual site.								

8) SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL			
FACTOR	POTENTIAL EROSION		
Point To Tuft Distance	LOW	MOD	HIGH
	≤4cm	>4cm - 6cm	>6cm
Distance – cm = 3cm	xxx		
Grass Standing Crop	HIGH		LOW
	<1500kg/ha	>1500kg/ha	
kg/ha = 5090		xxx	
OVERALL SOIL EROSION POTENTIAL		xxx	

9) VELD BURNING			
CATEGORY	%	BURN	
		YES	NO
DECREASER	14		
INCREASER I	42	xxx	
INCREASER II	19		
FUEL LOAD - kg/ha = 5090		xxx	
OVERALL DECISION TO BURN		xxx	

DECREASER SPECIES - species decrease with under or over grazing;

INCREASER I SPECIES - species increase with under grazing or selective grazing;

INCREASER II SPECIES - species increase with over grazing.

REFERENCE: W.S.W. Trollope & L.A. Trollope – Associates: Working On Fire International – 3rd April, 2009

Cell: 082 200 3373; Email: winfire@procomp.co.za.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS:

The Mean Grazing Capacity, current and recommended Stocking Rate and the Livestock Ratio are discussed on an overall farm basis and not for the individual sample sites.

**FLORA LISTS
GOEDGEVONDEN**

GOEDGEVONDEN FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
2	1	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
2	2	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium subsp.pilosellum</i>
2	3	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
2	4	<i>Hemizygia sp.</i>
2	5	<i>Commelina africana</i>
2	6	<i>Pelargonium luridum</i>
2	7	<i>Pearsonia cf.aristata</i>
2	8	Unknown
2	9	<i>Triumfetta sp.</i>
2	10	Unknown
2	11	<i>Rhynchosia adenodes</i>
2	12	<i>Commelina africana</i>
2	13	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
2	14	<i>Irididaceae sp.</i>
2	15	<i>Pearsonia cf.aristata</i>
2	16	<i>Gazania krebsiana</i>
2	17	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
2	18	<i>Fabaceae sp.</i>
2	19	<i>Hypoxis rigidula</i>
2	20	Unknown
2	21	<i>Triumfetta sp.</i>
2	22	<i>Crabbea cf.acaulis</i>
2	23	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
2	24	<i>Pearsonia cf.aristata</i>
2	25	Unknown
2	26	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>

< 1%	<i>Iridaceae sp.</i>
	<i>Pygmaeothamnus sp.</i>
	<i>Stachys sp.</i>
	<i>Cheilanthes viridis</i>
	<i>Conostomium natalense</i>

GOEDGEVONDEN FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species	
3A	1	<i>Pegolettia cf.lanceolata</i>	
3A	2	<i>Centella asiatica?</i>	
3A	3	<i>Helichrysum sp.1</i>	
3A	4	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium subsp.pilosellum</i>	
3A	5	<i>Oxalis depressa</i>	
3A	6	<i>Unknown</i>	
3A	7	<i>Unknown</i>	
3A	8	<i>Pteridium aquilinum</i>	
3A	9	<i>Hypochoeris radicata *</i>	
3A	10	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>	
3A	11	<i>Scabiosa columbaria</i>	
3A	12	<i>Lobelia flaccida</i>	
3A	13	<i>Rhynchosia adenodes</i>	
3A	14	<i>Richardia brasilense *</i>	
3A	15	<i>Hypericum aethiopicum</i>	
3A	16	<i>Unknown</i>	
3A	< 1%	<i>Gladiolus ecklonis</i>	Protected

GOEDGEVONDEN FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
3B	1	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
3B	2	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>
3B	3	<i>Barleria ovata</i>
3B	4	<i>Chaetacanthus burchellii</i>
3B	5	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
3B	6	<i>Senecio cf.consanguineus</i>
3B	7	<i>Acalypha angustata</i>
3B	8	<i>Crabbea sp.</i>
3B	9	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>
3B	10	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
3B	11	<i>Conyza sp.</i>
3B	12	<i>Schistostephium crataegifolium</i>
3B	13	Unknown
3B	14	<i>Schistostephium sp.</i>
3B	15	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
3B	16	<i>Raphionacme sp.</i>
3B	17	<i>Plantago major *</i>
3B	18	<i>Gerbera cf.piloselloides</i>
3B	19	<i>Dicoma anomala</i>
3B	20	<i>Thesium sp.</i>
3B	21	Unknown
3B	22	<i>Conyza bonariense *</i>
3B	23	<i>Triumfetta sp.</i>
3B	24	<i>Pearsonia cf.uniflora</i>
3B	25	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>
3B	26	<i>Zornia capensis</i>
3B	27	Unknown
< 1%		<i>Habenaria lithophila</i>

GOEDGEVONDEN FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species	
6	1	<i>Conyza cf.bonariense</i> *	
6	2	<i>Conyza albida</i> *	
6	3	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>	
6	4	<i>Hypericum aethiopicum</i>	
6	5	<i>Helichrysum cf.oreophilum</i>	
6	6	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>	
6	7	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>	
6	8	<i>Schizocarphus nervosus</i>	Protected
6	9	<i>Eriosema psoraleoides</i>	
6	10	<i>Rhynchosia cf.monophylla</i>	
6	11	<i>Zornia capensis</i>	
6	12	<i>Hypericum aethiopicum</i>	
6	13	<i>Hypoxis rigidula</i>	
6	14	Unknown	
6	15	<i>Gerbera sp.</i>	
6	16	<i>Gazania krebsiana</i>	
6	17	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>	
6	18	<i>Lobelia sp.</i>	
6	19	<i>Zornia capensis</i>	
6	20	Unknown	
6	< 1%	<i>Helichrysum candolleanum</i>	

FLORA LISTS
LA BELLA ESPERANZA

LA BELLA ESPERANZA FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
6	1	<i>Watsonia watsonioides</i>
6	2	<i>Helichrysum melanacme</i>
6	3	<i>Crotalaria cf.globifera</i>
6	4	<i>Acalypha angustata</i>
6	5	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
6	6	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i> complex
6	7	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i> var. <i>nudifolium</i>
6	8	<i>Asteraceae</i> sp.
6	9	<i>Zornia milneana</i>
6	10	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
6	11	<i>Conostomium natalense</i>
6	12	Unknown
6	13	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>
6	14	<i>Hyacinthaceae</i> sp.
6	15	<i>Pygmaeothamnus chamaedendrum</i>
6	16	<i>Eriosema cf.salignum</i>
6	17	Unknown
6	18	<i>Sonchus nanus</i>
6	19	<i>Eriosema cf.salignum</i>
6	20	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
6	21	Unknown
6	22	Unknown
6	23	<i>Helichrysum rugulosum</i>
6	24	Unknown
6	25	<i>Conyza pinnata</i>
6	26	<i>Alepidea peduncularis</i>
6	27	<i>Brunsvigia radulosa</i>

LA BELLA ESPERANZA FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
7	1	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
7	2	<i>Helichrysum melanacme</i>
7	3	<i>Rhynchosia sp.</i>
7	4	<i>Barleria ovata</i>
7	5	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
7	6	<i>Acalypha sp.</i>
7	7	Unknown
7	8	<i>Asteraceae sp.</i>
7	9	<i>Schistostephium crataegifolium</i>
7	10	<i>Rhynchosia totta</i>
7	11	<i>Commelina africana</i>
7	12	<i>Hibiscus aethiopicus</i>
7	13	<i>Rothea hirsuta</i>
7	14	<i>Acalypha sp.</i>
7	15	<i>Conyza bonariensis*</i>
7	16	Unknown
7	17	<i>Sonchus nanus</i>
7	18	<i>Fabaceae sp.</i>
7	19	Unknown

LA BELLA ESPERANZA FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
8	1	<i>Conostomium natalense</i>
8	2	<i>Senecio cf. polyanthemoides</i>
8	3	<i>Conyza bonariensis*</i>
8	4	<i>Solanum cf. anguivi</i>
8	5	<i>Bidens pilosa*</i>
8	6	Unknown
8	7	<i>Oxalis cf. semiloba</i>
8	8	<i>Verbena bonariensis*</i>
8	9	<i>Cucumis zeyheri</i>
8	10	<i>Asteraceae sp.</i>
8	11	<i>Zornia milneana</i>
8	12	<i>Sebaea grandis</i>
8	13	Unknown
8	14	<i>Richardia brasilense*</i>
8	15	<i>Tolpis capensis</i>
8	16	<i>Centella asiatica</i>
8	17	Unknown
8	18	<i>Conyza pinnata</i>
8	19	Unknown
8	20	<i>Bidens bipinnata*</i>
8	21	Unknown

LA BELLA ESPERANZA FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
9	1	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
9	2	<i>Barleria ovata</i>
9	3	<i>Acalypha punctata</i>
9	4	<i>Unknown</i>
9	5	<i>Monopsis decipiens</i>
9	6	<i>Chaetacanthus cf.burchellii</i>
9	7	<i>Rhynchosia sp.</i>
9	8	<i>Commelina sp.</i>
9	9	<i>Phyllanthus sp.</i>
9	10	<i>Unknown</i>
9	11	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>
9	12	<i>Unknown</i>
9	13	<i>Unknown</i>
9	14	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
9	15	<i>Oxalis sp.</i>
9	16	<i>Centella asiatica</i>
9	17	<i>Dicoma anomala subsp.circioides</i>
9	18	<i>Habenaria sp.</i>

FLORA LISTS
PAARDEPLAATS

PAARDEPLAATS FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
1A	1	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
1A	2	<i>Helichrysum cf. rugulosum</i>
1A	3	<i>Solanum panduriforme</i>
1A	4	<i>Fadogia tetraquetra</i>
1A	5	<i>Anthospermum hispidulum</i>
1A	6	<i>Conyza sp.</i>
1A	7	<i>Conyza albida</i>
1A	8	<i>Anthospermum cf. rigidum</i>
1A	9	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
1A	10	<i>Chaetacanthus burchellii</i>
1A	11	<i>Acalypha punctata</i>
1A	12	<i>Phymaspermum sp.</i>
1A	13	<i>Cucumis cf. hirsutus</i>
1A	14	<i>Verbena bonariensis *</i>
1A	15	<i>Conostomium natalense</i>
1A	16	<i>Gerbera ambigua</i>
1A	17	<i>Lobelia sp.</i>
1A	18	<i>Unknown</i>
1A	19	<i>Unknown</i>
1A	20	<i>Fabaceae sp.</i>
1A	21	<i>Watsonia watsonioides</i>
1A	22	<i>Crassula vaginata</i>

PAARDEPLAATS FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
1B	1	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
1B	2	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>
1B	3	<i>Barleria ovata</i>
1B	4	<i>Helichrysum sp.2</i>
1B	5	<i>Hypericum aethiopicum</i>
1B	6	<i>Ipomoea sp.</i>
1B	7	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
1B	8	<i>Rhynchosia monophylla</i>
1B	9	<i>Hypericum aethiopicum</i>
1B	10	<i>Acalypha punctata</i>
1B	11	<i>Acalypha punctata</i>
1B	12	<i>Conyza sp.aff. bonariense</i>
1B	13	<i>Aster sp.</i>
1B	14	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
1B	15	<i>Helichrysum pilosellum</i>
1B	16	<i>Rhus tomentosa</i>
1B	17	<i>Nidorella auriculata</i>
1B	18	<i>Eriospermum sp.</i>
1B	19	<i>Senecio oxyriifolius</i>
1B	20	<i>Acalypha angustata</i>

PAARDEPLAATS FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
2	1	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
2	2	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium var.pilosellum</i>
2	3	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
2	4	<i>Anthospermum hispidulum</i>
2	5	<i>Schistostephium cf.heptalobum</i>
2	6	<i>Thunbergia sp.</i>
2	7	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
2	8	<i>Helichrysum athrixiifolium</i>
2	9	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
2	10	<i>Acalypha punctata</i>
2	11	Unknown
2	12	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>
2	13	<i>Verbena brasiliense *</i>
2	14	<i>Conyza sp.</i>
2	15	<i>Conyza sp.2</i>
2	16	<i>Rhynchosia totta</i>
2	17	<i>Berkheya sp.</i>
2	18	<i>Commelina africana</i>

PAARDEPLAATS FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
4	1	<i>Fabaceae sp.</i>
4	2	<i>Oxalis depressa</i>
4	3	<i>Unknown</i>
4	4	<i>Unknown</i>
4	5	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>
4	6	<i>Helichrysum cf.athrixifolium</i>
4	7	<i>Helichrysum cf.athrixifolium</i>
4	8	<i>Rhynchosia totta</i>
4	9	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
4	10	<i>Unknown</i>
4	11	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
4	12	<i>Carthamus sp. *</i>
4	13	<i>Unknown</i>
4	14	<i>Gladiolus sp.</i>

FLORA LISTS
ZUURBRON

ZUURBRON FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
3A	1	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
3A	2	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>
3A	3	<i>Chaetacanthus burchellii</i>
3A	4	<i>Pelargonium luridum</i>
3A	5	Unknown
3A	6	<i>Helichrysum athrixiifolium</i>
3A	7	<i>Rhynchosia adenodes</i>
3A	8	<i>Crabbea sp.</i>
3A	9	<i>Triumfetta sp.</i>
3A	10	<i>Crabbea acaulis</i>
3A	11	<i>Felicia muriculata</i>
3A	12	<i>Hermannia floribunda</i>
3A	13	<i>Asteraceae sp.</i>
3A	14	<i>Sebaea cf. leiostyla</i>
3A	15	<i>Thunbergia atriplicifolia</i>
3A	16	<i>Eriosema sp.</i>
3A	17	Unknown
3A	18	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
3A	19	<i>Diospyros lycioides subsp. guerkei</i>
3A	20	<i>Berkheya sp.</i>
3A	21	<i>Asclepias sp.</i>
3A	22	<i>Dicoma anomala</i>
3A	23	<i>Anthospermum rigidulum</i>
3A	24	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
3A	25	<i>Argyrolobium pauciflorum</i>
3A	26	<i>Barleria ovata</i>
3A	27	<i>Cucumis sp.</i>
3A	28	<i>Hypericum aethiopicum</i>
3A	29	<i>Phyllanthus myrtaceus</i>
3A	30	<i>Gladiolus sp.</i>
3A	31	<i>Triumfetta sp.</i>
3A	32	<i>Hemizygia sp.</i>

ZUURBRON FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
6	1	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
6	2	<i>Helichrysum athriiifolium</i>
6	3	<i>Unknown</i>
6	4	<i>Phymaspermum acerosum</i>
6	5	<i>Sebaea grandis</i>
6	6	<i>Unknown</i>
6	7	<i>Wahlenbergia sp.</i>
6	8	<i>Conyza albida</i>
6	9	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
6	<1%	<i>Ledebouria apertiflora</i>
6	<1%	<i>Wahlenbergia cf.virgata</i>
6	<1%	<i>Verbena brasilense *</i>
6	<1%	<i>Hypoxis obtusa</i>
6	<1%	<i>Hesperantha leucantha</i>

ZUURBRON FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
7	1	<i>Verbena brasilense</i> *
7	2	<i>Acalypha punctata</i>
7	3	<i>Cineraria sp.</i>
7	4	<i>Conyza albida</i> *
7	5	<i>Hypochaeris radicata</i> *
7	6	<i>Aster sp.</i>
7	7	<i>Crabbea cf. acaulis</i>
7	8	<i>Chaetacanthus sp.</i>
7	9	<i>Commelina africana</i>
7	10	<i>Schistostephium heptalobum</i>
7	11	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>
7	12	<i>Helichrysum athrixiifolium</i>
7	13	<i>Hypoxis costata</i>
7	14	<i>Triumfetta sp.</i>
7	15	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
7	16	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
7	17	<i>Ledebouria sp.</i>
7	18	<i>Barleria ovata</i>
7	19	<i>Conyza asp.</i>
7	20	Unknown
7	21	<i>Hemizygia sp.</i>
7	22	<i>Leucosidea sericea</i>
7	23	<i>Anthospermum rigidulum</i>
7	24	<i>Sebaea cf. leiostyla</i>
7	<1%	<i>Thunbergia atriplicifolia</i>
7	<1%	Unknown
7	<1%	<i>Senecio cf. isatidioides</i>

ZUURBRON FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
8	1	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
8	2	Unknown
8	3	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>
8	4	<i>Diospyros lycioides subsp. guerkei</i>
8	5	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
8	6	<i>Crabbea sp.</i>
8	7	<i>Haplocarpha scaposa</i>
8	8	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>
8	9	<i>Helichrysum oreophilum</i>
8	10	<i>Diospyros lycioides subsp. sericea</i>
8	11	Unknown
8	12	<i>Scabiosa columbaria</i>
8	13	<i>Sebaea grandis</i>
8	<1%	<i>Conostomium natalense</i>
8	<1%	<i>Rubus sp.</i>
8	<1%	<i>Gnidia canoargentea</i>
8	<1%	<i>Sonchus dregeanus</i>
8	<1%	<i>Hypoxis obtusa</i>

FLORA LISTS
BERGVLIET

BERGVLIET FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
1	1	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
1	2	<i>Eriosema sp.</i>
1	3	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>
1	4	<i>Sebaea cf. leiostyla</i>
1	5	<i>Moraea sp.</i>
1	6	<i>Rhynchosia monophylla</i>
1	7	<i>Berkheya setifera</i>
1	8	<i>Vernonia natalensis</i>
1	9	<i>Commelina sp.</i>
1	10	Unknown
1	11	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>
1	12	Unknown
1	13	<i>Rhynchosia monophylla</i>
1	14	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>

BERGVLIET FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species
2	1	<i>Pegolettia cf. lanceolata</i>
2	2	<i>Wahlenbergia sp.</i>
2	3	<i>Pelargonium luridum</i>
2	4	<i>Pellaea calomelanos</i>
2	5	<i>Acanthaceae sp. (Chaetacanthus?)</i>
2	6	<i>Asteraceae sp.</i>
2	7	<i>Eriospermum sp.</i>
2	8	<i>Unknown</i>
2	9	<i>Unknown</i>
2	10	<i>Unknown</i>
2	11	<i>Phyllanthus myrtaceus</i>
2	12	<i>Sebaea natalensis</i>
2	13	<i>Bidens pilosa *</i>
2	14	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>
2	15	<i>Monopsis decipiens</i>
2	16	<i>Crotalaria cf.virgulata</i>
2	17	<i>Striga bilabiata</i>
2	18	<i>Pegolettia sp.</i>
2	19	<i>Conyza sp.</i>
2	< 1%	<i>Euryops pedunculatus</i>
2	< 1%	<i>Helichrysum candolleianum</i>
2	<1%	<i>Orobanchaceae sp.</i>
2	<1%	<i>Unknown</i>

BERGVLIET FLORA LISTS

Site No.	Sample No.	Species	
3	1	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>	
3	2	<i>Unknown</i>	
3	3	<i>Helichrysum nudifolium</i>	
3	4	<i>Schizocarphus nervosa</i>	Protected
3	5	<i>Unknown</i>	
3	6	<i>Zorna capensis</i>	
3	7	<i>Rhynchosia monophylla</i>	
3	8	<i>Moraea sp.</i>	
3	9	<i>Lobelia flaccida</i>	
3	10	<i>Helichrysum sp.</i>	
3	11	<i>Oxalis obliquifolia</i>	
3	12	<i>Thunbergia cf. atriplicifolia</i>	
3	13	<i>Rhynchosia sp.</i>	
3	14	<i>Unknown</i>	
3	15	<i>Hypochaeris radicata *</i>	
3	16	<i>Sebaea sp.</i>	

<1 %	<i>Kniphofia laxiflora</i>
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